
3D structural determination of glycans – mass spectrometric stochastic dynamics theoretical and experimental study[†]

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Abstract: The contribution attempts to render a plausible solution to problem of mass spectrometric based 3D structural analysis of carbohydrates such as glycans of fetal bovine serum. The research task is significantly difficult. Those carbohydrates show random variation of glycosylation and fucosylation processes; in addition to a lack of regioselectivity of processes leading to multicomponent polydisperse carbohydrates in mixtures, showing different length and skeletal modifications. Also, there are different isomers of those oligomers and polymers, including molecules, having linear and branches structures. Thus, the attempt to determine 2D and 3D structures of glycans, mass spectrometrically, is a challenging research task, even using newcomers in the analytical mass spectrometric instrumentation. The study persuasively shows that the application of the innovative mass spectrometric stochastic dynamic equation $D''_{SD} = 2.6388 \cdot 10^{-17} \cdot (I^2 - \langle I \rangle^2)$ shall yield reliable outcomes, due to the fact that it quantifies exactly fluctuations of the measurable variable intensity of analyte peaks over different spans of scan time. The formula produces the complete set of direct quantitative data on analyte concentration and its 3D conformation and electronic structure. The later task involves complementary Arrhenius's equation and computational quantum chemistry. The study deals with analysis of substituted glycans with 2-aminobenzamide. It utilizes high performance liquid chromatography and ultrahigh resolution electrospray ionization mass spectrometry, having orbitrap analyzer, as well as chemometrics.

Keywords: mass spectrometry; glycans; stochastic dynamics; 3D structural analysis; quantum chemistry.

1. Introduction

Protein glycosylation is post-translational modification in eukaryotic cells. The joined carbohydrates provide a significant amount of information about biological processes. They play key roles in cellular signaling pathways and cell-cell interactions, in addition to, their involvement in disease progression [1]. Important contributions to characterize biological activity of glycans and the affect on human disease have been carried out [2,3], thus determining their: (i) Structural and modulatory activity; (ii) intrinsic and (iii) extrinsic recognitions; and (iv) mimicry at a molecular level, respectively [4]. Both N- and O-glycosylation reactions are important for processes of protein folding, functionality and stability, respectively. Generally, three types of glycoproteins in mammalian such as N-, O- and C-glycans are known. Glycoconjugated analogous such as oligosaccharides, glycolipids and proteoglycans are known, as well. The glycan structural units of glycoproteins contain connected, mutually, monomeric CBs, where sequence, position and linkage type determine their diversity and complexity. Glycans exhibit significant variety

of isomers of oligomers and polymers. There are linear and branches CBs [5]. Due to significant structural similarity and bonding capability the structural analysis of glycan is a complex and challenging research task. However, *glycans* constitute *ca.* 70 % of mammalian cell proteins, which are glycosylated [5,6].

Sequencing of CBs oligomers by means of subsequent *exoglycosidase digestion* steps appears common technique capable of determining structure of complex CBs [1,7–9]. It allows us to distinguish between positional and linkage isomers. *Exoglycosidase enzymes* exhibit significant specificity toward monosaccharide unit and its linkage position, in addition to, its orientation (α versus β ,) respectively. They are capable of determining not only CBs sequence, but also their associated linkage and anomeric configuration. The *exoglycosidase matrix-based sequencing* of glycans is carried out *via* separation of products of matrix reactions. Often, it is performed by means of electrophoresis [10]. Structural information is obtained by examining peak shifts, due to a set of subsequent exoglycosidase treatments. A drawback of the method consists of rapidly loss of enzyme activity, thus, increasing significantly in cost of analyses [1].

Therefore, research areas of *glycomics* and *glycoproteomics* gain increasing attention. Their development allows *diagnostics* and *prognostics* of human diseases [2,3,11–21]. The comprehensive understanding of molecular level mechanistic aspects of glycosylation reactions improves diagnostics of human health and therapeutics efficiency of medications by means of quantifying and determining structurally biomarkers of glycans. Early stage reliable diagnostics of cancer can be performed *via* such as biomarkers [22–26]. Sialic acid bonding type ($\alpha_{2,6}$ - and $\alpha_{2,3}$ -linkages) has been connected with types of carcinoma cells. Presence of $\alpha_{2,6}$ -linked sialic acid has been found in biological fluids of patients with hepatitis B cirrhosis. Conversely, human samples of patients with hepatitis C cirrhosis show $\alpha_{2,3}$ -linked type sialic acids. Profiling of isomeric glycans might effectively discriminate between diseases [27].

The same is true for fucosylation process as potential marker for cancers and diseases. It is connected more directly with changes in disease [28]. Methodological developments, however, are challenging, due to the fact that fucosylation and glycosylation reactions in living cells are non-template-driven processes [29]. This causes for variously linked short and macromolecular, linear and branched CBs (**Figure S1**) [12,30–32].

There are a set of robust instrumental methods for separation and structural determination of complex mixtures of glycans such as high-performance liquid chromatography, mass spectrometry, ion mobility, (two-dimensional) electrophoresis, capillary electrophoresis, nuclear magnetic resonance, and high pH anion exchange chromatography equipped with pulsed amperometric detection, respectively [18,33–40]. A powerful method, amongst others, is *mass spectrometry* [41–46]. However, so far, is used mainly to quantify and determine 2D structurally glycans [21]. It is acknowledged that tandem mass spectrometric technique is, often, incapable of distinguishing between isomeric and isobaric structures of glycans [37]. Despite, it is important to distinguish among fragmentation MS techniques, showing complementary and highly extensive analytical structural information about CBs [38]. For instance, CID and infrared multi-photon dissociation cause chiefly for glycosidic bond cleavage. Generally, HCD and UVPD produce more information about analytes *via* rich-fragmentation MS patterns, comparing with CID and infrared multi-photon dissociation techniques [38,47]. Despite, product ions from CID and HCD can be nearly identical [38,48]. The two techniques employing tandem MS/MS operation mode show intramolecular rearrangement of glycans, leading to migration of Fuc- and Xyl-residues, as well [48]. Despite, underlined method capability of producing information-rich and specific MS patterns of analytes, many MS phenomena of UVPD-MS are still far from well-understood [48]. Nevertheless, UVPD together with tandem mass spectrometry, ion-mobility mass spectrometry, and electron detachment dissociation have been developed mainly for selective analysis of isomers of glycans [50,51].

Further: There should be mention free-radical-driven dissociation approaches such as radical-directed, electron transfer, electron capture, electronic excitation, and electron detachment dissociation, exhibiting prospective application to CBs structural characterization [38,52]. A coupled instrumental scheme involving HPLC equipped with Fs detection device and coupled to ESI-MS method improves significantly analysis of glycals, thus, providing highly specific structural information.

There have been developed a series of fluorescent labels used for glycan reductive amination. For instance, those are 2-aminobenzamide, 2-aminobenzoic acid, 2-aminoanthranilic acid, 1-aminopyrene-3,6,8-trisulfonic acid, IPC (**Figure S3**), RFMS, FRAG, 2-aminopyridine, procaine, and procainamide, respectively [37,38,53–55]. The 2-AB is widely used label compound [33,56,57], amongst other. Its major drawback consists of analyte poor ionization efficiency under ESI-MS conditions. Comparative analysis between this well-established labeled agent and procainamide labeled glycans has shown that in the latter case there is improvement of ionization efficiency [37,53,58]. The glycan analysis employing in RFMS as labeled compound has shown high-sensitivity toward Fs and ESI-MS detection [54,59]. Highly selective distinguishing between isomers, having subtle structural differences has been achieved using FRAGS reagent, examining their HCD and CID fragmentation patterns [38].

Herein, it is time, as well as, to provide more information about techniques such as, for example, solid-phase *permethylation*, reduction, and reductive amination, showing a set of advantages for MS based structural analysis of glycals [40,60,61]. Complementary application of reduction with permethylation to analyze N-glycans eliminates α , β , and γ -analyte anomers; thus, simplifying chromatographic analysis. There is improvement of MS ionization efficiency of analytes, comparing to 4-aminobenzoic acid butyl ester based process of reductive amination and reduction [40]. *Permethylation* removes O-acetylation of sialic acids, as well [40].

When, there is used MS method for analysis, then a data-base of MS spectra is processed *via searching or matching algorithms*, thus, annotating fragment species of glycans [62–64]. The effectiveness of method depends on database or MS spectra library [65] and searching algorithms, however, using a large scale of experimental conditions of measurements. The approach is time and labour consuming. Furthermore, the annotation software depends upon the type of chemically substituted glycans, and separation methods for multicomponent analysis of mixtures; thus, requiring an establishment of standard workflow of *glycomics* [66]. Moreover, the approach is characterized by a significant inaccuracy, because of the available software employs integrating peak area approach to process MS peaks of fragment ions [6]. The searching algorithms applied to interpret MS outcome of *glycomics* and *glycoproteomics* are chiefly similar to those used to *proteomics*. Therefore, they are adapted [67] and show effectiveness at about 50 % [68]. Also, annotation algorithms are inapplicable to determine 3D structurally glycans neither by means of Fs method, nor by NMR or MS ones. Improvement of method performances of searching algorithms has been obtained *via* employment in chromatographic and MS outcomes of RTs, complementary, thus, examining MS fragment ions ($|r|=0.998$) [11]. Despite, MS based profiling of glycans in human serum becomes popular [69].

Despite, superior MS method performances, comparing with aforementioned analytical instrumentation, conventional quantitative and molecular structural MS approaches to process MS data show low accuracy distinguishing isomers of glycan [70]. There are effort in employing specific MS fragments produced from CID-MS/MS method [70], however, often, these ions show low abundance (below.) High-mannose glycans have been identified through MS comparison with standard spectra of oligosaccharides; if any, and available data-bases. A logically derived sequence tandem mass spectrometry has been developed, as well. It involves CID-MS determination of alkali metal ion adducts and information about analyte dissociation mechanisms. The method does not require employment in standards [70]. Mass spectrometric molecular rearrangements of glycans have been comprehensively reviewed [29,71]. Despite, these methodological MS

developments and great capability of MS to determine glycans it is frequently very difficult to do so for fucosylated glycans. Due to, lability of Fuc-glycosidic bond, MS/MS might not distinguish core from antennary Fuc-derivatives; if any. A core-fucosylated derivatives on (GlcNAc)-fragment are distinguished, mass spectrometrically using site-specific information. However, the approach becomes, in fact, inapplicable to determine antennary Fuc-derivatives [28]. Despite, the latter study has shown that, when there is single Fuc-biantennary type substitution, then, there is a loss of (β -D-Gal)-unit in sialidase or sialidase/galactosidase digested N-glycans. Conversely, when there is single or double Fuc-tri-antennary type substitution, then fragment Fuc-(GlcNAc)-(β -D-Gal) appears stable, thus preventing a loss of (β -D-Gal)-residue. Also, it has been found that MS under positive polarity provides important structural information about glycans [72]. Despite, negative operation mode has been found as more useful to examine $[M_n+(H_2PO_4)_n]^-$ derivatives.

The above sketched observations and discoveries, so far, force us illustrate how our innovative mass spectrometric *stochastic dynamic* formulas (1) and (2) [73–76] contribute crucially to develop further the fields of *glycomics* and *glycoproteomics*. Their use to 3D molecular and electronic structural determination is carried out complementary with equation (3).

$$D_{SD}^{tot} = \sum_i^n D_{SD}^i = \sum_i^n \left(1.3194 \cdot 10^{-17} \cdot A^i \cdot \frac{\overline{I_i^2} - (\overline{I_i})^2}{(\overline{I_i} - \overline{I_i})^2} \right)$$

(1)

$$D_{SD}^{",tot} = \sum_i^n D_{SD}^{",i} = \sum_i^n \left(2.6388 \times 10^{-17} \times \left(\overline{I_i^2} - (\overline{I_i})^2 \right) \right)$$

(2)

$$D_{QC} = \left[\frac{\prod_{i=1}^{3N} v_i^{(0)}}{\prod_{i=1}^{3N-1} v_i^{(s)}} \right] \times e^{-\frac{\Delta H}{R \times T}}$$

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Therefore, it becomes clear that any statistical equation within the framework of relation $D_{SD}^{",tot} = f(D_{QC})$ determines unambiguously and exactly 3D molecular and electronic structures of analytes obtained as result from determination of MS intensity data on fragments under certain experimental conditions *via* equations (1) or (2). Despite, the general agreement between D_{SD}^{i} and $D_{SD}^{",i}$ parameters of equations (1) and (2) which has been tested, so far, [74,75], depending on complexity of the temporal behaviour of the MS variable *intensity* (function $(I - \langle I \rangle)^2 = f(t)$) over an examined span of scan time, there would be significant error contribution to D_{SD}^{i} data on equation (1), due to employment in SineSqr fitting function. Consider detail on calculation tasks according to formula (1) [77], which treat quantitatively MS spectra of cyclodextrins. The later contribution, therefore, is highly relevant to the content of this study. Equation (2) is derived from equation (1) as a simplistic formula, lacking of error contributions to $D_{SD}^{",i}$ parameters from chemometric treatment of experimental datasets of variables [46]. Within the framework of this fundamentally different quantitative processing and interpretation of MS variables is

achieved exact determination of analytes in mixture in solution with respect of their concentration [36,43,46,47]. Also, there is exact 3D structural analysis in the same mixture, when those equations are used to equation (3), complementary [42]. Its most recent application to quantify low molecular weight organics has shown $|r|=1$ [48,75,78,79]. Equation (2) has been used to quantify UVPD-MS data, as well [48] (Consider detail on works [48,68,73–79].) At this point, it should be said, only, that there is complete distinction between all known theories and model relations. The advantages of the later modes and their exact predictive and explanatory capability evaluated from perspective of quantitative chemometric criteria is demonstrate persuasively on the base on a statistically representative set of MS spectra of glycans (below.)

Before going on to results from this study, below, let us survey its goals, briefly: Multidimensional structural analysis of a set of complex CBs is carried out, mass spectrometrically, employing in high resolution soft ionization electrospray approach, computational quantum chemical methods SD model equations (1) and (2), respectively. The statistical significance of mathematical functionality among measurable mass MS parameters and theoretical data is evaluated quantitatively using *chemometrics*.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials and methods

2.1.1. Sample preparation and isotope labelling

The contribution uses experimental dataset of MS spectra of glycans of work [80]. There is used N-glycans obtained from modified *fetal bovine serum* (Fetuin, Sigma.) The corresponding raw (MASOP00220_AB_CRL_07JAN2021_Fetuin_001.d.zip) file can be downloaded free of charge [80][<https://zenodo.org/record/4705546>]. Its mass spectrum and total ion current is depicted in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Total ion current (TIC) versus time [mins]; mass spectrum of glycan at scan 17456 and retention time RT=40.520 mins.

We should underline a seemingly trivial issue of approach to product development processes of N-glycosylation associated with PNGase F used to the examined data on the current study, which is frequently used enzyme, amongst others, for N-linked CB release. This amidase cleaves between inner GlcNAc and asparagine fragment residue of tri-Man chitobiose core of almost all N-glycans from glycoproteins [81–83]. It a simple and rapid approach, which is characterized by highly specific cleavage capability; operates under mild experimental conditions; has long term operation stability; exhibits a lack of enzyme contamination after the process; enzyme repeated usage; and more [84]. The process is carried out in solution at $T=37^{\circ}\text{C}$. Methodological developments devoted to improvement of the reaction rate have concentrated on experimental factors such as, for example, mi-

crowave irradiation, fluids volume, pressure, *et cetera*. Details on preparation of PNGase F monolithic column can be found [85,86].

(Consider detail on sample preparation steps [80].)

2.1.2. Mass spectrometric measurements

The MS analysis of 2-AB labelled N-glycans was carried out by Agilent QTOF LC/MS/(MS), using Fs-detector. The MS/MS data on precursor ions, having charge states $z = (+2)–(+6)$ were analysed in ion trap. The calibration of the instrument has been carried out in 2GHz extended range (3000 m/z) in positive polarity. There has been used Agilent tuning mix. Separation step has been done on Acquity BEH Amide column, having 1.7 μm and 2.1 x 150 mm (Waters). The temperature of the column has been $T=45^\circ\text{C}$. There have been used the following solvents: 0.05% TFA in H_2O (A) and 0.05% TFA in CH_3CN (B), with flow rate at 500 $\mu\text{l}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. (Consider experimental design of the measurements in [80].).

Tandem MS/MS spectra have been obtained in positive polarity within the scan range: 300 to 3200 m/z and 100 to 3000 m/z. Fragmentor voltage has been 250 V; octopole RF voltage - 750 V; nozzle voltage - 3500 V, $T=225^\circ\text{C}$, drying gas flow rate - 18 $\text{L}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, nebulizer gas $P=35$ psig, and sheath gas $T=275^\circ\text{C}$, respectively.

Glycopeptide determination has been carried out by means of Dionex 3000 Ultimate nano-LC system (Dionex, Sunnyvale, CA) interfaced to orbitrap FusionTM LumosTM MS instrumentation (Thermo Fisher Scientific.) It has been equipped with a nano-ESI source. The separation step has been performed by PicoFrit C18 capillary column (75 μm id x 15 cm, New Objective). (Consider detail on sample measurements [80].)

2.1.3. Data availability

The experimental dataset of measurable variables is freely public available [80]. As aforementioned the current study represent complete and extended version of our short conference presentation [87,88]. The latter reference contains 33 % of the complete assignment and characterization both mass spectrometrically and quantum chemically of fragment ions of glycans. Moreover, it concentrates on MS characteristics chiefly of high Man-glycans (analyte (1), **Figure S2**). As can be expected, the current paper lacks of this knowledge, which can be seen in reference [87,88]. Also, there have been assigned nine species [87,88]. Conversely, the extended paper, herein discuss complete set of twenty seven fragment ions observed in mass spectra of N-glycans accounting for the effect of the proton accepting position, tautomeric and charge transfer effects of the species. Also, the current contribution distinguish quantitatively in chemometric terms MS characteristics and fragment ions of N- and O-glycans looking at data on analyte (8). This analysis lacks in presentation [87,88]. The conference presentation [87,88] shows 23 % of the quantitative analysis of structural determination of glycans within the framework of our theory and model equation (2) looking only at MS fragment species of analytes (8), (9) and (13), while the current paper contains the remaining at about 77 % of the experimental and theoretical results from analytes (2)–(13) (**Figure S2**.) Therefore, the current study provide persuasive empirical proof of our innovative stochastic dynamic theory and model equation (2) of its applicability to determine exactly 3D structures of so complex analytes such as N-glycans, thus highlighting on the base on a statistically representative set of both analytes as well as fragment ions their advantages over known database searching algorithms, which as our work shows clearly provide ambiguous information about even the carbohydrate subsequence of the monomeric units. As can be seen, often, there is 100 % score of assignment according to the known algorithms looking one at the same experimental datasets of MS variables for completely different glycan structures even looking the subsequence of hexose monomeric sub-units (consider, for example, cases of analytes (4a)–(4c), (9b) and (9c) as well as (13d) and (13e), respectively. Particularly, the latter two examples of assigned structures by means of known automated searching algorithm discussed in this study show probability 100 % assigning two completely different types of O- and N-glycans looking at one and the same datasets of MS variables. Those new data provided and described in the current study solved the

well-known drawback of the automated searching algorithm consisting on incapability of exact quantifying of low abundance MS ions. As can be seen from the new results of the current study our stochastic dynamic model equation (2) solves this problem unambiguously providing reliable results from perspective of chemometrics even examining structurally very similar glycans, exhibiting the same subsequence of CB units. As the new results have shown analyte (8) is determined 3D structurally according to our theory at a probability $|r|=0.9667_1$, despite the fact that the analyte RTs is overlapped with the data on analyte (2) as well as there is low abundance MS peaks of O-glycan at trace concentration levels.

2.2. Theory/Computations

Also, there are employed crystallographic data on glycans according to [89] (6MDS.pdb and 6MDV.pdb [<https://www.rcsb.org/structure/6MDS>].)

2.3. Chemometrics

(Consider references [90–92].)

Also, software ProteoWizard 3.0.11565.0 (2017), AMDIS 2.71 (2012) and mMass 5.5.0 was used.

3. Results

3.1. Mass spectrometric data

3.1.1. Major fragmentation routes of high-mannose type and complex glycans

The major fragmentation paths can be sketched, through a brief discussion on characteristic ions and examples of MS spectra with respect to increase complexity of analyte molecular structure. As we have seen from introductory section to this paper, there has been concentrated enormous research effort on MS methodology of determining structures of glycans. Many contributions, so far, provide a sound baseline for a systematic assignment of fragmentation paths of glycans. Despite, the aforementioned reasons difficult proper MS structural assignment of glycans, even employing ultra-high resolving power and superior method performances. Furthermore, there are multiply charged state species ($z=2-6$ in our case,) also detectable under tandem MS/MS mode [93], and mixed type Na^+ , K^+ , NH_4^+ and H^+ adducts, thus, causing for a constant challenge of examining their mixtures [12]. In order to demonstrate the capability of our innovative approach to distinguish among different metal-organic species of glycans a series of typically observed metal ion containing adducts are examined, herein, as well [94].

Let us begin by analysing high mannose type glycan $(\text{GlcNAc})_2(\text{Man})_5$. It is among most comprehensively examined derivatives (**Figure S2.**) The MS assignment uses the nomenclature detailed on [95–97]. Symbolic diagrams of N-glycans are proposed by Harvey and co-workers [98]. Analysis of its $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ adduct [99] shows that MS spectrum exhibit a dominating set of characteristic ions, produced *via* an internal fragmentations. A major cleavage yields to B_4 ion *via* loss of $(\text{GlcNAc})_2\text{-AB}$ fragment (m/z 1036.) To Y_1 ion belongs peak at m/z 364. Also, B_3 and Y_2 ions are at m/z 833 and 567. A loss of Man-residue from B_4 ion, occurs. (See detail on [99–102].)

The CID-MS/MS spectra provide direct unambiguous information about singly and multiply charged adducts and their fragmentation products associated with loss of Man-fragment in high-mannose glycans, also looking at m/z -difference ($\Delta m/z$) in values of fragment peaks, as well.

On the base on available comprehensive description of fragment paths of high-Man N-glycans from other authors there is carried out assignment of fragment ions of 2-AB substituted $(\text{GlcNAc})_2(\text{Man})_9$ analyte (m/z 772.3699; $z=3$) belonging to $[\text{M}-3\text{H}_2\text{O}+3\text{H}]^{3+}$ trication (1) (RT=15.38 mins and scans 3793–3796 of raw [80]; **Figures S3–S7.**) 2-AB substituted analytes of same type have been reviewed [102]. As can be seen, observed MS peaks agree well with results from [57,64,93,99–104]. Characteristic is MS peak at m/z 833 [98]. **Figures S3–S5** depict fragmentations of singly and doubly charged species of analyte (1), depending on labelling compound. 2-AB substituted analytes of type $(\text{GlcNAc})_2(\text{Man})_{10}$ are known [105–107] (**Figure S6**). High-Man glycan H_{11}N_2 has been deter-

mined in IgG [20]. There is peak at m/z 722 of trications $[M+H]^{3+}$. Peaks of $[M+Na]^+$ -adducts have been assigned, as well.

Examining of Glc-containing high-Man analytes can be found [108]. Reactions of $(Man)_5(GlcNAc)_2$ residue show subsequent loss of Man-fragment ($\Delta m/z=162$) produces peaks: m/z 870 \rightarrow 707.5, 707.5 \rightarrow 545.3, 545.3 \rightarrow 383.3 and 383.3 \rightarrow 221.2 reactions. The cleavage of $(Glc)_3$ is characterized by forming of trimeric, dimeric and monomeric ions.

Outlines of photo fragmentation reactions of high-mannose glycans associate peak at m/z 1865 with isomers of $(GlcNAc)_4(Man)_4$ and $(GlcNAc)_4(Man)_3(Gal)$ glycans [109]. Also, there are peaks at m/z 735 ($Y_{3\alpha}/Y_{3\beta}$), 1198 ($Y_{3\alpha}$) and 1403 ($Y_{3\alpha}$), respectively. A second isomer is distinguished, examining ions at m/z 1009 ($^{2,4}A_4$) and 1084.5 ($C_4/Z_{3\beta}$), while those at m/z 778 ($^{3,5}A_3$), 806 ($^{2,4}A_3$), 880 ($Z_{3\alpha}/C_3$ or D), 921 ($B_3/Y_{3\beta}$), 1109 ($^{3,5}X_2$) and 1471 ($^{1,5}X_{3\beta}$) belong to a third isomer. Therefore, detail on characteristic MS ions belonging to unique substitution type of glycans allows assignment of isomers in mixture, despite, complexity of structure.

What we have seen, so far, are major fragment paths of high-mannose N-glycans. Despite, complexity of the presented, so far, derivatives, there are significantly more serious problems of assigning other type glycans.

To begin with, there should be acknowledged typical peak at m/z 204 of cation $[(GlcNAc)]^+$. Also, there are peaks at 138 and 168 of products of $[(GlcNAc)]^+$ ion. The peak at m/z 657 is associated with $[(GlcNAc)-(Gal)-(Neu5Ac)]^+$ cation [110,111]. Since, MS 3D structural determination of glycans described in this paper involves ensemble of theoretical approaches based on chemometric linear correlation among MS results from equations (1) and (2), as well as, Arrhenius's diffusion data on equation (3) (**Figure S8**), at this point we are confronted with two major tasks. The first one determines common fragment MS ions, depending on molecular structure of analyte and its isomers. **Figure 2** shows characteristic MS ions and their assignment within m/z 100–1000. There lies a question: Do characteristic MS peaks change with increasing in complexity of the analyte molecular skeleton? In order to tackle this issue plausible and reliable, in addition to data on **Figure 3**, there are used reference m/z values of non- and labelled glycans: G0 (m/z 1317.5 and 1437.6, $(GlcNAc)_2(Man)_3(GlcNAc)_2$); G0F (1463.6 and 1583.6, $(GlcNAc)_2(Man)_3(GlcNAc)_2(Fuc)$); Man5 (1235.4 and 1355.5, $(Man)_5(GlcNAc)_2$); (1,6)G1F (1625.6 and 1745.7; $(GalGlcNAc)_2(Man)_3(GlcNAc)_2(Fuc)$); (1,3)G1F (1625.6 and 1745.7; $(GalGlcNAc)_2(Man)_3(GlcNAc)_2(Fuc)$); G2F (1787.6 and 1907.7; $(GalGlcNAc)_2(Man)_3(GlcNAc)_2(Fuc)$); G2FS1 (2077.8 and 2197.8; $(NeuNAc)(Gal)_2(GlcNAc)_2(Man)_3(GlcNAc)_2(Fuc)$ and G2FS2 (2368.9 and 2488.9; $(NeuNAc)_2(Gal)_2(GlcNAc)_2(Man)_3(GlcNAc)_2(Fuc)$, respectively [112]. There are examined glycans (2)–(13) (**Figures 3–7** and **S9–S13**, **Table 1**.) Due to, reasons mentioned before, analysis concentrates on description of Fuc-glycans (1), (6), (7) and (9)–(11), respectively.

Figure 2. A systematic representation of assignment of carbohydrate mass spectrometric fragment ions typically found in naturally occurring O- and N-glycans within mass-to-charge values m/z 100–2000; symbolic representation of carbohydrate moieties; the assignment has been carried out manually (see, for examples works [40,50,51,87,113–122], among others shown in the reference section.)

Analogously, examining of MS characteristics of multiple Fuc-substituents at core (GlcNAc) and on antennae units has been carried out [123–126]. Attention has been concentrated on Lewis_x and Lewis_y epitopes [124]. High-Fuc containing CBs show loss of fragment $\Delta m/z=146$ when there are singly charged ions [123]. Processes involving doubly charged ions exhibit loss of $\Delta m/z=71$. Peaks at m/z 680 and 522 are of charged species or sodium adducts. 3-Antenna CBs reveal peaks at m/z 424, 570, and 716 of (Gal)(GlcNAc)-moiety and Fuc-residues. Peak at m/z 716 belongs to ^{1,3}A_{3a} fragment of hepta-Fuc triantennary glycan [124]. The MS peak at m/z 570 is abundant, when mono-Fuc-fragment occurs. The study examines species at m/z 591.5 ($z=3$) ((6)) and 590.8 ($z=2$) ((7)) (**Figure S10(A).**) MS database based annotation of (7) shows reliability 90–100 % of structures shown in **Figure S10(B).** *Chemometrics* of twenty-four m/z and absolute average intensity variables of peaks of (6) and (7) yield to $|r|=1$ and 0.9889₄ (**Figure S14.**) ANOVA tests of data on (6) and (7) shows that they are not significantly different (**Tables 2 and S1.**) Peaks at m/z 504 and 731 are assigned according to [125]. The α -2,6 and α -2,3 linkage [27] of CBs is examined in case of ion at m/z 308. It could be assigned to [(Gal)(Fuc)]⁺ ion under ESI(+)-MS. In case of (8) peak at m/z 308 can be associated with [NeuGc]⁺ ion or its dimer [(NeuGc)₂]²⁺. MS spectrum of (8) is difficult to be assigned precisely only looking at a single analyte analysis.

Figure 3. Mass spectra of analytes (3) and (4); symbolic diagrams of molecular structures annotated according to [105]; matching score [%]; chemical diagrams of most probably molecular structure according to this work (chemical diagrams of all glycans examined, herein, are depicted in **Figure S2** and below.)

Furthermore, [105] shows score 94.73 % of proposed structure and MS pattern. Moreover, there is a lack of annotation of peaks of (NeuGc)₂ and oligomer (n<10) sub-units of CBs. The same is true for (NeuAc)_n (n<10) moieties. Despite, they are found in naturally occurring CBs [105,127–130]. The analytes show score between MS patterns and structures looking at (NeuAc)₂ or (NeuGc)₂ subunits as followings: Glycan (2), 99.29%, (NeuGc)₂; (3), 100.00%, (NeuAc)₂; (4), 100.00%, (NeuGc)₂ or (NeuAc)₂; (5), 91.08% (NeuGc)₂ or 99.02 % (NeuAc)₂; (8), 94.73%, (NeuGc)₂; and (10), 100.00%, (NeuGc)₂ moiety; or there are 54.54% dimer (NeuGc)₂ or (NeuAc)₂ with statistical probability 91.08–100%. Homooligomeric CBs are known [108]. For instance, there is (Neu5Ac)₃ trimer [131]. Therefore, we examine MS ions of such peaks; if any. Analytes (12) and (13) show annotation score according to [105]: Glycan (12), 89.73%, (NeuGc)₄; and (13) 69.77% (NeuGc)₄ and 88.29% (NeuAc)₃, respectively. In case of (13) there is score 100 % of MS peaks, thus proposing structures (13d) and (13e). Despite, the virtual identical MS shapes of (5) and (13) there is proposed (13c), showing accuracy 93.67%. Probably, the structure corresponds to spectrum of (5), having score 99.66 %. **Figure S7** shows that (5), (13) and (12) exhibit peaks at m/z 291, 395 and 566, which can be assigned to [NeuAc]⁺ [131,132], [(NeuAc)₂]²⁺ or BZ fragment of [(NeuGc)]⁺ (m/z 291;) dication of ^{2,5}A_{NeuAc} ion [(NeuAc)₂]²⁺ or dimer [(NeuGc)₂]²⁺ (m/z 395;) and ^{1,5}A_{NeuGc} fragment of ion [NeuGc]⁺ or BZ of type [(NeuAc)₂]⁺ (m/z 566), respectively. **Figures 5** and **6** and **Table S2** provide proof of linear relation with a statistical significance looking at measurable variables of (5), (12) and (13) of ions at m/z 291, 395 and 566, respectively. Chemometrics of peaks of (5) and (13) show

$|r|=0.6862$, thus deducing that MS spectrum of (13) belongs to (13d) (see **Figure S2**,) rather than to (13e). Annotation of (13) to MS pattern of (5) yields to accuracy of 60 %. Thus, despite, virtually identical MS patterns of (5) and (13) intensity ratios of their MS peaks are significantly different. Peak at m/z 366 can be assigned to $^{0,4}\text{ANeuAc}$ of NeuAc-self-associate of (5). Glycan (8) does not show a set of peaks at m/z 291, 395 and 566. Despite, [105] shows score 94.73 % of subunit (NeuGc)₂. The same is true for peak at m/z 308 of [(Gal)(Fuc)]⁺ in (8). It is not detected of (9) (m/z 1007 ($z=4$)) despite, that coverage between MS peaks and structure according to [105], showing 100 %. In order to tackle those variations among annotation algorithm [105] and experimental MS data on (9) there is used assignment of ions shown in [56], where at RT=65 mins 2-AB labelled CBs have Fuc-residue. Glycan (9) is characterized by complex MS pattern showing m/z 407 of [(Gal)(GalNAc)]⁺ ion, however, it can be assigned to [(HexNAc)₂]⁺ ion, as well [105–107]. It is assigned to N,N'-diacetylactosamine (LacdiNAc)-modified glycans, as well [128]. Peak at m/z 274 of ion [Neu5Ac]⁺ [131–134] shows loss of solvent molecule. Chemical reactivity of (Neu5Ac)-containing glycans indicates a lactone formation reaction of Neu5Ac-CBs [2] (**Figure S15**.)

Figure 4 Chemical diagrams of mass spectrometric species of monomeric and dimeric N-acetylneuraminic acid (NeuAc), elemental composition of the species; theoretical m/z data and intensity ratio of the peaks of the isotope shape.

Let us consider further, how chemometrics evaluation of relation $D''_{SD}=f(D_{QC})$ might respond to highly reliable assignment of MS spectra of CBs, exhibiting virtually identical MS fragments. For instance, those are species (4) (m/z 1107.1256, $z=3$), (10) (1107.4603, $z=3$) and (11) (m/z 1107.7969, $z=3$), respectively. They are particularly illustrative examples of capability of our innovative approach to annotate and determine 3D structurally glycans employing in experimental MS and computational quantum chemistry as well as equations (1)–(3). First, (4), (10) and (11) show peak at m/z 657 of $[(\text{Neu5Ac})(\text{Gal})(\text{GalNAc})]^+$ ion, while (10) shows m/z 695 of $[(\text{Neu5Gc})(\text{Gal})(\text{GalNAc})+\text{Na}]^+$ cation. Second, (11) has different possible structures, however, producing annotation score 100% [105].

Finally, chemometrics of a statistically representative set of ten peaks (**Table 1** and **Figure S16**) of (4), (10) and (11) produce $|r|=1-0.9278_2$. The results from ions at m/z 291, 395 and 566 of (5), (12) and (13) produce $sd(yEr\pm)$ values listed in **Table 3**. MS peaks at m/z 138, 168, 204 and 274 showing $sd(yEr\pm)$ values deviation at the five digits. The assignment is performed looking at [135,136].

Figure 5. Correlation among total intensity data (I ; [arb.units]) on **Table S2** of ions at m/z 291, 395 and 566 of analytes (5), (12) and (13); proposed symbolic structures of analytes according to automated annotation software [105]; chemometrics.

3.1.2. Determination of mass spectrometric stochastic dynamic parameters

Table S3 shows measurable variables of analyte ions *per* short span of scan time, while **Table S4** lists data on equations (1) and (2). (see calculation tasks of formula (1) [77].) $\ln P1$ parameter is constant equal to $\ln P1 = 17.053$ [73–79]. Since, the paper addresses a question whether measurable variables obey equation (2) as a certain law, as well as, **Figure 7** depicts correlative analysis of D'_{SD} and D''_{SD} data, showing $|r|=0.9976_4$ and 0.8818 of (8). There is compatibility of equations (1) and (2) (**Figure S17**.) Despite, deviation from $|r|=1$ of relation $D''_{SD}=f(D'_{SD})$ the $\ln P1$ value remains also constant in MS spectra of glycans. ($P1$ represents a random number, see equation (A2.2) (p.291) [137].) A value $|r|=1$ of function $D''_{SD}=f(D'_{SD})$ is achieved looking at ions at m/z 291, 292, 395 and 566 of (5), (12) and (13), respectively (**Table S4**.) The relation of ions of (13) at m/z 138, 153, 168, 186 204, 274 281, and 366 yields to $|r|=0.9921_8$.

The function between D''_{SD} data on latter glycans by pairs show $|r|=0.9999_8$ (5)/(13) and $|r|=0.5145_4$ (12)/(13) (**Figure S18**.) Decreasing in statistical significance in cases of (12) and (13) agree well with the proposed annotation of observable ions. If there are assigned peaks at m/z 291/292, 395 and 566 to monomer and dimer (NeuAc)-species, then this explain the $|r|=0.9999_8$ correlating data on (5) and (13). The species have (NeuAc)₂- subunit annotated at a score 99.02 % in (5). Analyte (12) lacks of (NeuAc)₂-unit, but there is proposed oligomer (NeuGc)_n-moiety. Value $|r|=0.5145_4$ assumes different dimer and oligo-

mer (NeuAc)₂ and (NeuGc)_n self-associates in (5) and (12). Relation $D''_{SD}=f(D^{iSD})$ of (10) yields to $|r|=0.9312_1-0.9984_8$, while analyte (11) shows $|r|=0.9983_7$. The chemometrics of relation between D''_{SD} parameters of (6) and (7) show $|r|=0.9852$.

Figure 6. Correlation among total intensity data (I ; [arb.units]) on **Table S2** and diffusion D''_{SD} [$\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$] parameter of equation (2) of ions at m/z 291, 395 and 566 of analytes (5), (12) and (13); chemometrics.

Figure 7 illustrates relation $D''_{SD}=f(I^{TOT})$ of fragment ions of (8) (**Table S4**), yielding to $|r|=0.97$. Owing to the fact that D^{iSD} is determined precisely *per* short span of scan time ($t=0.18$ s in (8)), it becomes clear that I^{TOT} values of both quantitative and 3D structural analyses causes for deviation from $|r|=1$, as well. Moreover, chemometrics of $D''_{SD}=f(I^{TOT})$ function in cases of (12) and (13) show $|r|=0.1841_8$ and 0.7000_8 (**Tables S4** and **Figure S19**). Chemometrics of (10) produce $|r|=0.6512_4-0.9833_2$. High $|r|$ -parameter is obtained, excluding from data on ion at m/z 274. Results from (11) yield to $|r|=0.9921_3$ looking at peaks at m/z 138, 168, 204 and 274, respectively.

Figure 7. Correlation among total intensity data (I ; [arb.units]) on **Table S2** and diffusion D''_{SD} [$\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$] parameter of equation (2) of ions of analytes (2), (8), and (11); chemometrics

3.2. Theoretical quantum chemical data

3.2.1. Molecular and electronic structures as well as energetics of ions of glycans

This subsection presents an in-depth theoretical analysis of relation among 3D molecular conformation, electronic structure and energetics of fragmentation ions of glycans (1)–(13). It provides important insights into molecular factors and electronic effects governing most stable 3D molecular structure corresponding to minimum of PES at ground state, which is used to calculate D_{OC} -values of equation (3). The issue is linked to an important theme in chemical reactivity of CBs, since, there are studied proton and CT effects, in addition to, intramolecular rearrangement and cyclization reactions; if any. In moving in the latter direction, we can start the sub-section, underlying that static and MD computations employed, herein, use mainly adiabatic Born-Oppenheimer approximation. There is examined PES in ground and transition states. PESs map molecular geometry with respect to electronic energy within the framework of the aforementioned approximation. Thus, there is detailed on relation between 3D geometry and energetics of the molecular systems.

Having so far considered, we should underline important advantage of employment in equations (2) and (3). It drastically increases capability of mass spectrometry of determining 3D structures of enantiomers. It is well-known that enantiomers exhibit exactly the same energy values and physico-chemical properties, thus, excluding from optical rotation values [138]. Intensity data on MS ions reflect physicochemical properties. Therefore, MS shapes of enantiomers are virtually identical. However, the *fluctuations* of the measurable variables are different. Also, exactly equal energy data on enantiomers unable we to use only *GS free Gibbs energy* data, in order to, distinguish between enantiomers. Formula (3) uses vibrations of molecular species of TSs. Thus, it can distinguish accurately among enantiomers *via* D_{OC} -parameters. Exact predictive power of first-order saddle point of molecular vibrations is often difficult, due to inaccuracy of the interatomic potentials. Often, there are used anharmonic and harmonic parts of PES [139]. Nevertheless, computation of PES of TSs allows us to detail precisely on thermal molecular motions and their fluctuations using MD, thus, distinguishing between subtle electronic effects of enantiomers in TSs. Highly accuracy results from PES can be achieved *via*

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ab initio and DFT approaches [140]. The latter method shows comparable accuracy of 3D molecular structure, diffusion data and energetics to the *gold standard* or CCSD(T) approach to CBS limit [141]. The M06-2X 6-311++G(2d,p) method yields to comparable accuracy of energy of organics comparing with CCSD(T)/aug-ccpVTZ and CCSD(T)-CBS methods [142], showing energy difference $\Delta E = |2| - |1| \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$.

Before, to illustrate the latter line of pro-arguments for powerful explanatory and predictive capability of relationship $D''_{SD}=f(D_{QC})$ let us consider briefly the accuracy of low cost computational quantum chemical methods, thus allowing us to evaluate the error contribution to D_{QC} and geometry parameters, due to theoretical quantum chemical method. **Figure S20** depicts linear relationships between geometry parameters of oxonium [Fuc]⁺ cation obtained due to loss of solvent water molecule obtained at M062X/SDD and M062X/STO-3G level of theories. As can be seen there are $|r|=0.99952$. The corresponding data on the same cation obtained *via* PM6 approach yield to $|r|=0.99677$. Detail on affect on theoretical method on D_{QC} values are shown in next sub-section 3.2.2.

The second very important thing to say in this sub-section is that frequently charged species of CBs exhibit intramolecular proton and CT effects associated with rearrangement. Series of singly charged and dications of monomer and dimer of (NeuAc)_n and (NeuGc)_n (n=1-2) (**Figures 8** and **S21**) show that, often, an intramolecular cyclization occurs. Oxonium cation of peak at m/z 292 of [(NeuAc)]⁺ exhibits most stable geometry, showing covalent bond formation between O-centre from C⁷-OH substituent and C²-(COOH) centre of oxonium ion. The CT-effect results in stabilization of C²⁺-cation (**Figure 8(A)**, **Tables S5–S7**.) The same process is observed examining theoretically ion m_{292_b}, producing thermodynamically more favourable cyclic product. There is a difference in total energy $\Delta E^{TOT}=|0.006201| \text{ a.u.}$ A cyclization reaction has been found examining most stable 3D ionic structure of m_{274_b} cation (**Figure 8(B)**), as well. Again, the initial state of oxonium cation appears less preferred, thermodynamically. There is a covalent bonding of O-centre of C⁷-OH position accompanied with a CT effect. Cation m_{274_a} is less stable than ionic species m_{274_b} at $\Delta E=|0.036| \text{ a.u.}$

Figures S22–S31 depicts a representative set of calculated observable fragmentation species of glycans depending on their tautomeric forms and proton accepting positions. The corresponding atomic coordinates of the species in GS and TS; their thermochemical data and frequencies are summarized in **Tables S5–S7** as mentioned above.

3.2.2. Determination of quantum chemical diffusion parameters

In order to tackle the discussed issue adequately, examining relatively large carbohydrates there are correlated data on D_{QC} -values of equation (3) of oxonium cations of monomeric α L-Fuc, β D-Man, α D-Gal, and α D-Xyl species toward different levels of theory (**Tables S8, S9** and **Figure S32**.) The correlative analysis between D_{QC} parameters of M062X/SDD and M062X/STO-3G levels of theory show $|r|=0.9199$, while correspondence with results from former method and PM6 shows $|r|=0.339–0.991$ [143–148]. Those results agree with computational outcome of enzymes at PM6 level of theory showing decreasing in sensitivity of molecular conformation and energetics with quantum mechanics methods. However, there remains unclear whether conclusions can be approximated to different molecular species or implementations of the PM6 computations [147,148]. As our results show, chemometrics parameter can vary drastically. For this reason, correlation between D''_{SD} and D_{QC} data on glycans shown, herein, is carried out using high accuracy DFT method for relatively small systems and low m/z-values, as well as, PM6 computations when relations treat species having large m/z-region. At this point it should be make an explicit remark that any function $D''_{SD}=f(D_{QC})$ discussed in the study is obtained within one theoretical method in computing D_{QC} -values. Therefore, corresponding statistical equations reflect only concrete level of theoretical approach. Thus, the correlative data on species having higher than m/z 650 (**Figures S24, S25, S27–S31**) is carried out employing PM6 level of theory.

The small difference in total energy of ions m_{292_a} and m_{292_b} of $\Delta E^{\text{TOT}} = |0.006201|$ a.u., causes for a significantly large ΔD_{QC} parameter of the latter ion showing difference $\Delta D_{\text{QC}} = |45.64|$ (Table 4). As can be seen, the D_{QC} parameter reflect significantly more sensitive the subtle electronic effects, which improves drastically the method performances, hen here is used the relationship $D^{\text{SD}} = f(D_{\text{QC}})$.

Figure 8. Theoretical quantum chemical static and molecular dynamics data on fragmentation species of glycans; total energy E^{TOT} [a.u.] with respect to optimization step number, potential energy [a.u.] versus time in trajectory [fs], most stable 3D molecular structures of species; chemical diagrams of reactions of intramolecular rearrangement

3.3. Correlative analysis between theory and experiment

The subsection concentrates on correlative D^{SD} and D_{QC} data on fragmentation ions of glycans (2)–(13) (Figures 9 and 10.) As indicated in Table 4 D_{QC} parameters according highly sensitively to any conformational chance and perturbation of electronic structures of carbohydrate isomers and enantiomers. However, drawing on above discussion on accuracy of theoretical quantum chemical data and its error contribution to D_{QC} -parameters, an outline of results from chemometrics of $D^{\text{SD}} = f(D_{\text{QC}})$ of analytes (2)–(13) shall be given. As can be seen, there are obtained chemometric data $|r| = 0.9838$ – 0.99982 examining statistically representative sets of MS fragments of analytes. The latter parameters, particularly, indicates excellent-to-exact correlation between D^{SD} and D_{QC} data on equations (2) and (3). We should, in the course of this subsection, further, examine the affect of different conformations and protonated forms of the MS species on the chemometric $|r|$ -parameter, thus illustrating the refutation of hypothesized structures by quantitative criteria of chemometrics. The correlative analysis of function $D^{\text{SD}} = f(D_{\text{QC}})$ of analyte (8) looking at MS ions at m/z 138, 168, 204, 274 and 292 taking into consideration the corresponding protonated forms of those ions labelled as 138_b , 168_b , 204_a , 274_b and 292_b yields to $|r| = 0.9892$ (see the D_{QC} data on those species listed in Table 4.) One can take $D_{\text{QC}} = 3148.7931$ belonging to fragment ion of

N-glycolylneuraminic acid (292_d form) instead of sialic acid. The chemometric parameter in this case is decreased in $|r|=0.2704$. The same is true for examining $D''_{SD}=f(D_{QC})$ relation of analyte (13) looking at data on MS peaks at m/z 186, 204 and 292, showing $|r|=0.9998$. The corresponding cations forms of those species are 186_a, 292_b and 204_a, respectively. The chemomeric data on ion at m/z 292, however, assessing the molecular cation 292_d yields to $|r|=0.984$. Following the logical consequence of our theory let us examine low abundance species at m/z 308, 366 and 407 in addition to the shown above set of MS peaks. The liner correlation in this case shows in the latter case $|r|=0.5093$. In parallel, however, the relationship $D''_{SD}=f(D_{QC})$ of the species at m/z 308, 366 and 407 is characterized by $|r|=0.9667$ (**Figure 8**.) On the base on those results we propose that the two datasets of MS peaks belong to two different carbohydrate specie, which are not completely separated chromatographically looking at the overlapped peaks of analytes (2) and (8) or there is impurity of O-glycan. In order to gain further pro-arguments an evidence of our latter statement we carry out independent analysis of the experimental dataset of measurable variables of analyte (8) by GlycoWorkbench tool [105] showing that if the datasets of MS peaks are assigned to one and the same molecule then the matching score is 87 % (**Table S10, Figures S7 and S33**.) Conversely, if two sets of MS peaks are regarded as belonging to two different molecules then, the shown in Figure 8 symbolic diagram of analyte (8) is characterized by annotation score 100 % (**Figure 33**.) Thus, we underline that the illustrated persuasively owing to the fact that there is obtained $|r|=0.9998$ logic of refutation of hypothesized molecular structure of complex analytes such as glycans by means of chemometric assessment of the relation $D''_{SD}=f(D_{QC})$ of parameters of equations (2) and (3) provide a reliable framework of innovative model relations that solve a set of most important problems of structural determination of glycans including not only their exact 3D conformation and electronic structural analysis, but also determination of mixtures of analytes. The data on glycans (3) and (11) are $|r|=0.9855_3$ and 0.9979_1 examining MS peaks at m/z 186, 204, 274, 292 (3) and 138, 168, 204, 292 (11).

Figure 9. Correlation of $D''_{SD} [cm^2 \cdot s^{-1}]$ and D_{QC} parameters of equation (2) and (3) of glycans (5) and (8); chemical and symbolic diagrams of glycan (8).

Figure 10. Correlation of D''_{SD} [$\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$] and D_{QC} parameters of equations (2) and (3) of glycans (2), (9) and (13), respectively.

Table 1

Average mass spectrometric variables of CID-MS/MS spectra of ions at m/z 1107 ($z=3$) at scans: 7186–7190 ((4), m/z 1107.1257, $z=3$), 7242–7248 ((11), m/z 1107.7969, $z=3$), and 7333–7337 ((10), m/z 1107.4603, $z=3$), respectively. There are four data-sets of variables *pro* range of scans.

(4)		(10)		(11)	
m/z	I [arb.units]	m/z	I [arb.units]	m/z	I [arb.units]
138.05605	4242.94312	138.05611	7476.58862	138.05609	3755.59548
168.06665	3067.32134	168.06682	6369.88208	168.06671	2935.26344
204.08815	7033.00328	204.08801	10659.19009	204.08803	5534.86714
274.09402	4385.6719	274.09415	7629.009	274.09381	3319.88284
366.142	6276.87221	366.17905	7024.55323	366.14105	4504.55224
657.18805	883.84695	657.22003	1664.1297	657.13904	710.91924
1186.599	2294.07571	1186.64502	4461.28063	1186.70911	1231.95608
1251.12903	3412.26552	1251.15808	5320.49878	1251.05505	1841.41835
1332.23303	5297.51315	1332.151	7042.71475	1332.28601	4563.61951
1844.84583	795.57315	1844.66602	1502.58796	1844.83411	580.55922
		695.3653	511.08568		
		1682.60608	780.19624	1654.01611	1031.36031

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Table 2

One way ANOVA chemometric outcomes of m/z data on analytes (4), (6), (7), (10) and (11); H₀ - null hypothesis (The means of all selected datasets are equal;); H₁ - alternative hypothesis (The means of one or more selected datasets are different)

Data on analytes (4) and (11)						
Dataset	N	Mean	sd(yEr±)	se(yEr±)		
	10	742.24418	612.13826	193.57511		
	10	742.2469	612.14448	193.57708		
Source	DoF	SS	MS	F-value	P-value	
Model	1	3.7004.10 ⁻⁵	3.70046.10 ⁻⁵	9.87535.10 ⁻¹¹	0.99999	
Error	18	6744907.00	374717.055			
At the 0.05 level, the population means are not significantly different.						
Levene's Test for Equal Variance						
Model	1	234.718766	234.718766	2.19644.10 ⁻⁹	0.99996	
Error	18	1.9235386.10 ¹²	1.068632.10 ¹¹			
At the 0.05 level, the population variations are not significantly differ						
Data on analytes (4) and (10)						
Dataset	N	Mean	sd(yEr±)	se(yEr±)		
	10	742.24418	612.13826	193.57511		
	10	742.23243	612.09684	193.56202		
Source	DoF	SS	MS	F-value	P-value	
Model	1	6.90606.10 ⁻⁴	6.906061.10 ⁻⁴	1.84315.10 ⁻⁹	0.99997	
Error	18	6744382.14	374687.897			
At the 0.05 level, the population means are not significantly different.						
Levene's Test for Equal Variance						
Model	1	10412.3269	10412.3269	9.7465.10 ⁻⁸	0.99975	
Error	18	1.9229643.10 ¹²	1.06831.10 ¹¹			
At the 0.05 level, the population variations are not significantly differ						
Data on intensities of peaks of analytes (6) and (7)						
Dataset	N	Mean	sd(yEr±)	se(yEr±)		
	24	198560.92921	198998.50833	40620.40041		
	24	147612.30282	151463.44282	30917.3458		
Source	DoF	SS	MS	F-value	P-value	
Model	1	3.11491504.10 ¹⁰	3.11491504.10 ¹⁰	0.99611	0.32347	
Error	46	1.438456.10 ¹²	3.1270790.10 ¹⁰			
At the 0.01 level, the population means are not significantly different.						
Means Comparison using Bonferroni Test						
Dataset	Mean	Difference between means	Simultaneous confidence intervals		Significant at 0.01 level	
			Lower limit	Upper limit		
Data1_(6)	198560.9					
Data1_(7)	147612.3	50948.6264	-86218.06194	188115.31474	No	
Data on m/z of peaks of analytes (6) and (7) (Table S4)						
Dataset	N	Mean	sd(yEr±)	se(yEr±)		
	24	469.66303	273.63311	55.85512		
	24	469.66303	273.63313	55.85513		
Source	DoF	SS	MS	F-value	P-value	
Model	1	4.366648.10 ⁻¹¹	4.36664878.10 ⁻¹¹	5.83191.10 ⁻¹⁶	1.00000	

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Error	46	3444253.70	74875.0805		
At the 0.01 level, the population means are not significantly different.					
Means Comparison using Bonferroni Test					
Dataset	Mean	Difference between means	Simultaneous confidence intervals		Significant at 0.01 level
			Lower limit	Upper limit	
Data1_(6)	469.6630				
Data1_(7)	469.6630	1.90758.10 ⁻⁶	-212.25008	212.25009	No

Table 3

Mean values, standard deviations (sd(yEr±)) and standard errors (se(yEr±)) of measurable variables m/z of analytes (4), (10) and (11)

Mean	sd(yEr±)	se(yEr±)
138.05608	2.92702.10 ⁻⁵	1.68992.10 ⁻⁵
168.06673	8.51285.10 ⁻⁵	4.91489.10 ⁻⁵
204.08806	7.51892.10 ⁻⁵	4.34105.10 ⁻⁵
274.09399	1.6955.10 ⁻⁴	9.78899.10 ⁻⁵
366.15403	0.02167	0.01251
657.18237	0.04079	0.02355
1186.65104	0.0553	0.03193
1251.11405	0.05312	0.03067
1332.22335	0.06802	0.03927
1844.78198	0.1006	0.05808

Table 4

Theoretical D_{QC} data on equation (3) accounting for different forms of fragmentation species annotated to mass spectrometric observable peaks of glycans

m/z	Form	D _{QC}	m/z	Form	D _{QC}
138	138_b	135.5037 ₇₉	168	168_b	56.6548
407		184426.5211	168	168_c	137.8581
186	186_a	110.8916	308		416.9386
	186_FucNa ⁺	141.7072	368		87.41123
291	291_a	184.8312 ₅	204	204_a	590.6082
	291_c	44.9376		204_b	53.6261 ₀₄
292	292_a	32.6495 ₉	274	274_a	120.3697 ₅
	292_b	78.2906 ₈		274_b	174.4939 ₉
	292_d	3148.7931	488		48.4341
366	366_bg_a	18.8329 ₈	566	566_a	121461.3468
	366_bg_b	160158.2365	472	472_α _{2,6}	18.2031
	366_yb_a	59.6433 ₈		472_α _{2,3}	12.6738 ₉₄

366_yb_b	117.5081	366	366_yy_a		73.8458
			366_yy_b		255.4406

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4. Discussion

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Our first task in section Discussion is to shed more light on the problem of accurate and exact determination of D_{QC} parameters of equation (3), which is, particularly, highlighted examining complex CBs such as glycans. In the latter context, enormous research effort has been concentrated on solving the problem of computing accurately single-point energies of molecules by means of quantum chemical approaches [143]. Remarkable achievements has resulted to current routine obtaining of thermochemistry with chemical accuracy, however, for small-to-relatively medium-sized molecules, employing methods such as, for example, Gn and Wn ones. Since, the thermochemistry is associated with computation of molecular vibrational frequencies, logically, calculation of D_{QC} data on comparable accuracy to chemical one is achievable, currently, however, examining LMWs. From perspective of the current study, an employment in those methods is computationally prohibitive and expensive research task. Moreover, computation of thermochemical parameters (Tables S5 and S8) involves several steps. Of course, there are developed many semi-empirical methods. They show comparable error contribution to thermochemistry ~ 15 kJ.mol⁻¹. Hybrid-DFT approaches show error contribution to D_{QC} ~ 2 -5 kJ.mol⁻¹. Calculation of vibrational modes of molecular system containing, for instance, 320 heavy atoms are ~ 4 times faster, when there is used semi-empirical methods [143,144], comparing with DFT approaches. Particularly, accuracy of PM6 method [145] looking at its data on enthalpy of formation of a representative set of 1373 compounds involving elements H, C, N, O, F, P, S, Cl, and Br has been accounted for 4.4 kJ.mol⁻¹ [144,145]. Semi-empirical QM shows poor method performance in examining noncovalent bond interactions [146]. The PM6 approach yields to 10.6 kJ.mol⁻¹ error to energetics of noncovalent interacting ensembles. Its improved version PM6-D3H4, however, produces error accounted for 1.4 kJ.mol⁻¹. PM6 data on interaction energy of oligomers of amino acids show standard deviation 15.5–25.5 kJ.mol⁻¹ correlating its results with those obtained via B3LYP-D3 method [146]. PM6 shows standard deviations |5.1|–|17.6| kJ.mol⁻¹ (see Table 2 in [146].) The results presented in preceding sections show that correlation of geometry parameters obtained via PM6 and M062X/SDD yield to $|r|=0.9967$.

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Therefore, employment in balancing methods between computational cost and accuracy is of significant importance, computing fragment MS species of glycans, particularly, concentrating on fragmentation ions, having high m/z -values and multiply charges. Often, for such systems, low cost theoretical calculation of vibrational modes appears unavoidable. Owing to the fact that utilization for low-cost methods for vibrational analysis provides different challenges for molecular species with significant conformational flexibility such as CBs, for purposes of this study, it is of important to access relations among D''_{SD} -data with respect to different theoretical methods; if any. For this reason, we correlate data on low-cost quantum chemical methods with results from M062X/SDD approach, examining monomeric CB units (see Figure S32.) As can be seen, there is $|r|=0.9913$ looking at data on sto-3g basis set. The results from PM6 are characterized by $|r|=0.33$ – 0.91 , depending on the molecular structure of the CB species. Those chemometric parameters should be accounted for evaluating relationship $D''_{SD}=f(D_{QC})$ of parameters of equations (2) and (3) depicted in Figures 9 and 10, because of the deviation of its $|r|=1$ is, due to error contribution to D_{QC} parameter.

In what follows, we draw on advantages of our innovative *stochastic dynamic theory* and model equation (2), providing arguments for their best theorizing of mass spectrometric phenomena of glycans furnishing to us by theoretical methods developed by other authors, so far. In doing so let us begin by providing brief description of the important ideas behind formula (2). Thus, the stochastic dynamic theory and its basic equations (1) and (2) derive from the *theory of random variables*. It states that temporal distribution of measurable MS variables exhibit random character and obeys equation (1) as a certain MS law. The measurable MS parameters are characterized by so-called *fluctuations* of their mean values which cannot be neglected neither qualitatively nor quantitatively. Therefore, they should be quantified. This can be carried out by means of equation (1). The formula fills logical gap between experimental MS observations, showing variation of mean values of both mass-to-charge (m/z) and intensity parameters of fragmentation molecular species. Since, a major purpose of scientific theory and model formula are not only to explain observable phenomena, but also to predict them exactly from perspective of chemometrics, quantitative description of MS phenomena within the framework of equation (1) rooted in Box-Mueller method [149,150]. It represents a stochastic dynamic approach capable of generating random values and introduces the so-called *variance* of random variables. Our modification of the basic Box-Mueller formula has resulted to equation (1) (see detail on [41–47].) Since, the formula contains a statistical parameter A_i , due to SineSqr approximation of experimental relation between measurable parameter intensity (I) of MS peak of fragment ions of analytes with respect to short span of scan time (t) or function $(I - \langle I \rangle)^2 = f(t)$, which, however, contribute to error of chemometric data-processing of experimental results to diffusion parameter D''_{SD} of equation (1), we further have simplified, as aforementioned, equation (1) to equation (2). Equation (2) is an exact MS law lacking from error of data-processing of measurable variables to D''_{SD} parameter. It has been evidenced empirically looking at a series of works that equation (2) quantifies exactly analytes in solution, thus, producing $|r|=1$. Also, as mentioned before, another bridging capability of equations (1) and (2), which has found experimental proof is that our MS laws are capable of determining exactly 3D molecular and electronic structures of analytes when they are used complementary with equation (3). From perspective of chemistry under *three dimensional molecular structure* (or 3D structure of a molecule) there is understood quantities of *geometrical parameters* which are bond lengths, torsion and dihedral angles of atoms of molecules which connect those position of 3D space exhibiting maximum value of electron density and showing, in parallel, minimum *free Gibbs energy* of ensemble of atoms forming molecule within the framework of Born-Oppenheimer approximation. In other words, *3D molecular and electronic structures* are experimentally justifiable and observable sets of geometry parameters and 3D electron density maps, determining positions in 3D space, which are characterized with maximum of electron density of atoms in molecules. The determined 3D structure of any molecule is an observational and empirically justifiable statement derived from experimental data. (Consider, for instance, detail on [151].)

From perspective of this study, it is important to underline that mathematical algorithms used to annotate glycans on the base on MS observable parameters lack of quantification of *fluctuations* of measurable variables. The matching algorithms use mass of theoretical fragmentation ion and experimental m/z mean value obtained after deconvolution without to account for its variation. The matching information, obtained on the base on so-called *score*, in fact, represents quantitative parameter assessing, again, mean value of intensity, thus lacking from quantitative description of its variation [152–170]. Despite, enormous contributions devoted to methodological developments of matching algorithms and MS databases for automated assignment of molecular structures of glycans and glycopeptides such as, for example, GlycoPep DB, Glyco-Pep ID, GlycoPep grader, GlycoPeptide-Search, GlycoPep Detector, GlycoMaster DB, Glycopeptide Finder, SweetSEQer, UniCarb-DB, Peptonist, Cartoonist, GlycanGUI, GlycoMod, Protein Pro-

spector, Integrated Glyco-Proteome Analyzer, GlycoFragWork, pGlyco, Sweet-NET, Sweet-Heart, UNIFI, SimGlycan, GPQuest, MAGIC, NglycDB, MoFi, glyXtoolMS, Toolbox Accelerating Glycomics (TAG), GlycoQuest, Byonic, GRITS Toolbox, Proteome Discoverer v1.4, MSFragger, and more [152–170], no version of other theoretical MS descriptions of observable phenomena and model equations developed, so far, which quantify exactly MS measurable variables, thus accounting precisely for fluctuations of measurable variables. To the fields of *glycomics* and *glycoproteomics*, therefore, equations (1) and (2) represent a novelty, contributing crucially for further methodological developments and innovations of quantitative description of MS data on glycans and their reliable quantification and structural determination, because of comparing to most recent innovations of the field of quantitative analysis of glycans showing $r^2=0.999$ [171], the chemometrics show that at about 85 % of quantitative analyses based on equation (2) show exact $|r|=1$ parameter [73–79].

5. Conclusions

In this study, for the first time in the literature, we have argued in detail examining functional relationship between diffusion data on our innovative stochastic dynamic theory and model equation (2) that it provides exact treatment of experimental measurable variables m/z and intensity values of mass spectrometric fragment of glycans in complex multicomponent mixture and, further, furnishes reliable analytical information about the 3D molecular conformation and electronic structures of those analytes when it is used complementary to Arrhenius's equation (3). There is obtained excellent-to-exact chemometric parameter showing $|r|=0.9998$. The credibility of the logical consequence of our theory and chemometric examining of relationship $D'_{SD}=f(D_{QC})$ has been proven evaluating a set of different proposed protonated forms of carbohydrate species belonging to different observable mass spectrometric peaks, accounting not only for their proton accepting position, but also molecular conformations, tautomerism, charge and proton transfer effects as well as intramolecular rearrangement reactions; if any. Further, we have evidenced, that the chemometric analysis of relationship $D'_{SD}=f(D_{QC})$ is capable of distinguishing quantitatively and reliably among sets of mass spectrometric peaks observable in mixtures of analytes belonging to different molecules. The excellent chemometric data on applying our theory and model equation (2) to determine 3D structurally so significantly complex analytes such as glycans give illustrates persuasively their prospective application to many interdisciplinary research field providing reliable and valid probabilistic inferences and determinations those class of naturally occurring and synthetic complex carbohydrate macromolecules.

Supplementary Materials: Experimental mass spectrometric and computational data (**Figures S1–S33** and **Tables S1–S10**).

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ABBREVIATIONS

ANOVA		Analysis of variances
APCI		Atmospheric pressure chemical ionization (mass spectrometry)
CBs		Carbohydrates
CID		Collision induced dissociation (mass spectrometry)
CT		Charge transfer
DFT		Density functional theory
ESI		Electrospray ionization (mass spectrometry)
FRAGS		Free-radical-activated glycan-sequencing reagent
Fuc	▼	Fucose
Fs		Fluorescence
GS		Ground state
Gal	●	Galactose
GalNAc	■	N-acetyl galactosamine
Glc	●	Glucose
GlcNAc	■	N-acetylglucosamine
HCD		Higher-energy collisional dissociation
HILIC		Hydrophilic interaction liquid chromatography
IPC		InstantPC™ (instant glycan labeling organic dye)
IgG		Immunoglobulin G
I ^{TOT}		Total mass spectrometric intensity
LMWs		Low molecular weight (analytes)
MALDI		Matrix assisted laser desorption ionization (mass spectrometry)
MD		Molecular dynamics
MM		Molecular mechanics
Man	●	Mannose
MS		Mass spectrometry
NeuAc	◆	N-acetylneuraminic acid/ Sialic Acid
NeuGc	◇	N-glycolylneuraminic acid
NMR		Nuclear magnetic resonance
PT		Proton transfer
PES		Potential energy surface
RTs		Retention times
RFMS		RapiFluor-MS
r		Coefficient of linear correlation (chemometrics)
SD		Stochastic dynamics
sd(yEr±)		Standard deviation (chemometrics)
se(yEr±)		Standard error (chemometrics)
TIC		Total ion current
TS		Transition state (first saddle point)
2-AB		2-aminobenzamide
2-AA		2-aminobenzoic acid

References

- [1] R. Farsang, N. Kovacs, M. Szigeti, H. Jankovics, F. Vonderviszt, A. Guttman, Immobilized exoglycosidase matrix mediated solid phase glycan sequencing, *Anal. Chim. Acta* 1215 (2022) 339906.
- [2] A. Araujo, V. Castro, R. Reis, R. Pires, Glucosamine and its analogues as modulators of amyloid- β toxicity, *ACS Med. Chem. Lett.* 12 (2021) 548–554.
- [3] J. Munkley, The glycosylation landscape of pancreatic cancer, *Oncol. Lett.* 17 (2019) 2569–2575.
- [4] Y. Xie, M. Butler, Construction of an Instant PC-derivatized glycan glucose unit database: A foundation work for high-throughput and high-sensitivity glycomic analysis, *Glycobiol.* 32 (2022) 289–303.
- [5] D. Harvey, Matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization mass spectrometry of carbohydrates, *Mass Spectrometry Reviews* 18 (1999) 349–451.
- [6] M. Goli, A. Yu, B. Cho, S. Gautam, J. Wang, C. Gutierrez-Reyes, P. Jiang, W. Peng, Y. Mechref, LC-MS/MS in glycomics and glycoproteomics analyses, chapter 8; In book: *Carbohydrate Analysis by Modern Liquid Phase Separation Techniques* (2021) Elsevier, Amsterdam.
- [7] S. Chen, D. Wu, C. Robinson, W. Struwe, Native mass spectrometry meets glycomics: resolving structural detail and occupancy of glycans on intact glycoproteins, *Anal. Chem.* 93 (2021) 10435–10443.
- [8] D. Demus, P. Urbanowicz, R. Gardner, H. Wu, A. Juszczak, T. Stambuk, E. Medvidovic, K. Owen, O. Gornik, N. Juge, D. Spencer, Development of an exoglycosidase plate-based assay for detecting α 1-3,4 fucosylation biomarker in individuals with HNF1A-MODY, *Glycobiol.* 32 (2022) 230–238.
- [9] I. Walsh, T. Nguyen-Khuong, K. Wongtrakul-Kish, S. Tay, D. Chew, T. Jose, C. Taron, P. Rudd, GlycanAnalyzer: software for automated interpretation of N-glycan profiles after exoglycosidase digestions, *Bioinformatics* 35 (2019) 688–690.
- [10] S. Wagt, N. de Haan, W. Wang, T. Zhang, M. Wuhler, G. Lageveen-Kammeijer, N-glycan isomer differentiation by zero flow capillary electrophoresis coupled to mass spectrometry, *Anal. Chem.* 94 (2022) 12954–12959.
- [11] Y. Hu, T. Shihab, S. Zhou, K. Wooding, Y. Mechref, LC-MS/MS of permethylated N-glycans derived from model and human blood serum glycoproteins, *Electrophoresis* 37 (2016) 1498–1505.
- [12] N. Suzuki, T. Abe, K. Hanzawa, S. Natsuka, Toward robust N-glycomics of various tissue samples that may contain glycans with unknown or unexpected structures, *Sci. Rep.* 11 (2021) 6334.
- [13] L. Wei, Y. Cai, L. Yang, Y. Zhang, H. Lu, Duplex stable isotope labeling (DuSIL) for simultaneous quantitation and distinction of sialylated and neutral N-glycans by MALDI-MS, *Anal. Chem.* 90 (2018) 10442–10449.
- [14] S. Zhou, X. Dong, L. Veillon, Y. Huang, Y. Mechref, LC-MS/MS analysis of permethylated N-glycans facilitating isomeric characterization, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 409 (2017) 453–466.
- [15] G. Lageveen-Kammeijer, N. de Haan, P. Mohaupt, S. Wagt, M. Filius, J. Nouta, D. Falck, M. Wuhler, Highly sensitive CE-ESI-MS analysis of N-glycans from complex biological samples, *Nat. Commun.* 10 (2019) 2137.
- [16] C. Ashwool, C. Lin, M. Thaysen-Andersen, N. Packer, Discrimination of isomers of released N- and O-glycans using diagnostic product ions in negative ion PGC-LC-ESI-MS/MS, *J. Am. Soc. Mass Spectrom.* 29 (2018) 1194–1209.
- [17] A. Everest-Dass, D. Kolarich, M. Campbell, N. Packer, Tandem mass spectra of glycan substructures enable the multistage mass spectrometric identification of determinants on oligosaccharides, *Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom.* 27 (2013) 931–939.
- [18] B. de Toro, W. Peng, A. Thompson, Gema Dominguez, F. Javier Casada, J. Perez-Castells, J. Paulson, J. Jimenez-Barbero, I. Canales, Avenues to characterize the interactions of extended N-glycans with proteins by NMR spectroscopy: The influenza hemagglutinin case, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 57 (2018) 15051–15055.
- [19] F. Tousei, J. Bones, W. Hancock, M. Hincapie, Differential chemical derivatization integrated with chromatographic separation for analysis of isomeric sialylated N-glycans: A nano-HILIC-MS platform, *Anal. Chem.* 85 (2013) 8421–8428.
- [20] A. Marie, S. Ray, S. Lu, J. Jones, I. Ghiran, A. Ivanov, High-sensitivity glycan profiling of blood-derived immunoglobulin G, plasma, and extracellular vesicle isolates with capillary zone electrophoresis-mass spectrometry, *Anal. Chem.* 93 (2021) 1991–2002.
- [21] H. Park, J. Jung, E. Rodrigues, E. Kitova, M. Macauley, J. Klassen, Mass spectrometry-based shotgun glycomics for discovery of natural ligands of glycan-binding proteins, *Anal. Chem.* 92 (2020) 14012–14020.
- [22] N. Seo, H. Lee, M. Oh, G. Kim, S. Lee, J. Ahn, H. Cha, K. Kim, J. Kim, H. An, Isomer-specific monitoring of sialylated N-glycans reveals association of α 2,3-linked sialic acid epitope with Behcet's disease, *Front. Mol. Biosci.* 8 (2021) 778851.
- [23] J. Prien, D. Ashline, A. Lapadula, H. Zhang, V. Reinhold, The high mannose glycans from bovine ribonuclease B isomer characterization by ion trap MS, *J. Am. Soc. Mass Spectrom.* 20 (2008) 539–556.
- [24] C. Nwosu, H. Yau, S. Becht, Assignment of core versus antenna fucosylation types in protein N-glycosylation via procainamide labeling and tandem mass spectrometry, *Anal. Chem.* 87 (2015) 5905–5913.
- [25] S. Zhou, Y. Huang, X. Dong, W. Peng, L. Veillon, D. Kitagawa, A. Aquino, Y. Mechref, Isomeric separation of permethylated glycans by porous graphitic carbon (PGC)-LC-MS/MS at high temperatures, *Anal. Chem.* 89 (2017) 6590–6597.
- [26] Y. Peng, L. Wang, Y. Zhang, H. Bao, H. Lu, Stable isotope sequential derivatization for linkage-specific analysis of sialylated N-glycan isomers by MS, *Anal. Chem.* 91 (2019) 15993–16001.
- [27] Y. Huang, S. Zhou, J. Zhu, D. Lubman, Y. Mechref, LC-MS/MS isomeric profiling of permethylated N-glycans derived from serum haptoglobin of hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) and cirrhotic patients, *Electrophoresis* 38 (2017) 2160–2167.

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- [28] H. Yin, J. Zhu, J. Wu, Z. Tan, M. An, S. Zhou, Y. Mechref, D. Lubman, A procedure for the analysis of site-specific and structure-specific fucosylation in alpha-1-antitrypsin, *Electrophoresis*. 37 (2016) 2624–2632. 893
- [29] M. Wuhrer, A. Deelder, Y. van der Burgt, Mass spectrometry of glycan rearrangements, *Mass Spectrom. Rev.* 30 (2011) 664–680. 895
- [30] X. Sun, L. Tao, L. Yi, Y. Ouyang, N. Xu, D. Li, R. Linhardt, Z. Zhanga, N-glycans released from glycoproteins using a commercial kit and comprehensively analyzed with a hypothetical database, *J. Pharmaceut. Anal.* 7 (2017) 87–94. 896
- [31] E. Mucha, A. Stuckmann, M. Marianski, W. Struwe, G. Meijera, K. Pagel, In-depth structural analysis of glycans in the gas Phase, *Chem. Sci.* 10 (2019) 1272–1284.. 897
- [32] H. Lu, Y. Zhang, P. Yang, Advancements in mass spectrometry-based glycoproteomics and glycomics, *National Science Review* 3 (2016) 345–364. 898
- [33] J. Ahn, J. Bones, Y. Yu, P. Rudd, M. Gilar, Separation of 2-aminobenzamide labeled glycans using hydrophilic interaction chromatography columns packed with 1.7 μ m sorbent, *J. Chromatogr. B* 878 (2010) 403–408. 899
- [34] E. Green, G. Adelt, J. Baenziger, S. Wilson, H. Van Halbeek, The asparagine-linked oligosaccharides on bovine fetuin, *J. Biol. Chem.* 263 (1988) 18253–18268. 900
- [35] D. Fu, L. Chen, R. O'Neill, A detailed structural characterization of ribonuclease B oligosaccharides by ¹H NMR spectroscopy and mass spectrometry, *Carbohydr. Res.* 261 (1994) 173–186. 901
- [36] Y. Yu, T. Tyrikos-Ergas, Y. Zhu, G. Fittolani, V. Bordoni, A. Singhal, R. Fair, A. Grafmgller, P. Seeberger, M. Delbianco, Systematic hydrogen-bond manipulations to establish polysaccharide structure-property correlations, *Angew. Chem.* 131 (2019) 13261–13266. 902
- [37] R. Kozak, C. Tortosa, D. Fernandes, D. Spencer, Comparison of procainamide and 2-aminobenzamide labeling for profiling and identification of glycans by liquid chromatography with fluorescence detection coupled to electrospray ionization-mass spectrometry, *Anal. Biochem.* 486 (2015) 38–40. 903
- [38] R Murtada, K. Fabijanczuk, K. Gaspar, X. Dong, K. Alzarieni, K. Calix, E. Manriquez, R. Bakestani, H. Kenttaemaa, J. Gao, Free-radical-mediated glycan isomer differentiation, *Anal. Chem.* 92 (2020) 13794–13802. 904
- [39] G. Lageveen-Kammeijer, E. Rapp, D. Chang, P. Rudd, C. Kettner, J. Zaia, The minimum information required for a glycomics experiment (MIRAGE): reporting guidelines for capillary electrophoresis, *Glycobiology* 32 (2022) 580–587. 905
- [40] Y. Guan, M. Zhang, J. Wang, H. Schlueter, Comparative analysis of different N-glycan preparation approaches and development of optimized solid-phase permethylation using mass spectrometry, *J. Proteome Res.* 20 (2021) 2914–2922. 906
- [41] M. Grabarics, M. Lettow, C. Kirschbaum, K. Greis, C. Manz, K. Pagel, Mass spectrometry-based techniques to elucidate the sugar code, *Chem. Rev.* 122 (2022) 7840–7908. 907
- [42] A. Gavriilidou, K. Sokratous, H. Yen, L. De Colibus, High-throughput native mass spectrometry screening in drug discovery, *Front. Mol. Biosci.* 9 (2022) 837901. 908
- [43] W. Peng, F. Kobeissy, S. Mondello, C. Barsa, Y. Mechref, MS-based glycomics: An analytical tool to assess nervous system diseases. *Front. Neurosci.* 16 (2022) 1000179. 909
- [44] D. Campos, M. Girgis, M. Sanda, Site-specific glycosylation of SARS-CoV-2: Big challenges in mass spectrometry analysis, *Proteomics* 22 (2022) 2100322. 910
- [45] J. Li, B. Guo, W. Zhang, S. Yue, S. Huang, S. Gao, J. Ma, J. Cipollo, S. Yang, Recent advances in demystifying O-glycosylation in health and Disease, *Proteomics* 22 (2022) 2200156. 911
- [46] I. Bagdonaite, S. Malaker, D. Polasky, N. Riley, K. Schjoldager, S. Vakhrushev, A. Halim, K. Aoki-Kinoshita, A. Nesvizhskii, C. Bertozzi, H. Wandall, B. Parker, M. Thaysen- Andersen, N. Scott, Glycoproteomics *Nat. Rev. Meth.* 2 (2022) 48. 912
- [47] D. Wang, J. Baudys, J. Bundy, M. Solano, T. Keppel, J. Barr, Comprehensive analysis of the glycan complement of SARS-CoV-2 spike proteins using signature ions-triggered electron-transfer/higher-energy collisional dissociation (ETHcD) mass spectrometry, *Anal. Chem.* 92 (2020) 14730–14739. 913
- [48] B. Ivanova, M. Spiteller, Stochastic dynamic ultraviolet photofragmentation and high collision energy dissociation mass spectrometric kinetics of triadimenol and sucralose, *Environ. Sci. Poll. Res.* (2023) [<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-24259-z>] 914
- [49] E. Hecht, P. Loziuk, D. Muddiman, Xylose migration during tandem mass spectrometry of N-linked glycans, *J Am Soc Mass Spectrom.* 28 (2017) 729–732. 915
- [50] E. Escobar, S. Wang, R. Goswami, M. Lanzillotti, L. Li, J. McLellan, J. Brodbelt, Analysis of viral spike protein N-glycosylation using ultraviolet photodissociation mass spectrometry, *Anal. Chem.* 94 (2022) 5776–5784. 916
- [51] D. Ropartz, M. Fanuel, S. Ollivier, A. Lissarrague, M. Benkoulouche, L. Mulard, I. Andre, D. Guieysse, H. Rogniaux, Combination of high-resolution multistage ion mobility and tandem MS with high energy of activation to resolve the structure of complex chemoenzymatically synthesized glycans, *Anal. Chem.* 94 (2022) 2279–2287. 917
- [52] R. Murtada, S. Finn, J. Gao, Development of mass spectrometric glycan characterization tags using acid-base chemistry and/or free radical chemistry, *Mass Spec Rev.* (2022) e21810 918
- [53] S. Klapoetke, J. Zhang, S. Becht, X. Gu, X. Ding, The evaluation of a novel approach for the profiling and identification of N-linked glycan with a procainamide tag by HPLC with fluorescent and mass spectrometric detection, *J. Pharmaceut. Biomed. Anal.* 53 (2010) 315–324. 919
- [54] C. Reed, J. Fournier, N. Vamvoukas, S. Koza, Automated preparation of MS-sensitive fluorescently labeled N-glycans with a commercial pipetting robot, *SLAS Technol.* 23 (2018) 550–559. 920
- [55] M. Alley Jr., C. McManus, Y. Yu, S. Hallinan, J. Gebler, P. Rudd, Glycan characterization of the NIST RM monoclonal antibody using a total analytical solution: From sample preparation to data analysis, *mAbs*, 9 (2017) 1349–1359. 921

- [56] F. Higel, U. Demelbauer, A. Seidl, W. Friess, F. Soergel, Reversed-phase liquid-chromatographic mass spectrometric N-glycan analysis of biopharmaceuticals, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 405 (2013) 2481–2493. 953
954
- [57] R. Kozak, C. Tortosa, D. Fernandes, D. Spencer, Comparison of procainamide and 2-aminobenzamide labeling for profiling and identification of glycans by liquid chromatography with fluorescence detection coupled to electrospray ionization-mass spectrometry, *Anal. Biochem.* 486 (2015) 38–40. 955
956
957
- [58] C. Nwosu, H. Yau, S. Becht, Assignment of core *versus* antenna fucosylation types in protein N-glycosylation *via* procainamide labeling and tandem mass spectrometry, *Anal. Chem.* 87 (2015) 5905–5913. 958
959
- [59] H. Deris, A. Cindric, M. Lauber, T. Petrovic, A. Bielik, C. Taron, M. van Wingerden, G. Lauc, I. Trbojevic-Akmacic, Robustness and repeatability of GlycoWorks RapiFluor-MS IgG N-glycan profiling in a long-term high-throughput glycomic study, *Glycobiology*, 31 (2021) 1062–1067. 960
961
962
- [60] S. Gautam, W. Peng, B. Cho, Y. Huang, A. Banazadeh, A. Yu, X. Dong, Y. Mechrefm, Glucose unit index (GUI) of permethylated glycans for effective identification of glycans and glycan isomers, 145 (*Analyst*) 6656–6667. 963
964
- [61] B. Cho, W. Peng, Y. Mechref, Separation of permethylated O-glycans, free oligosaccharides, and glycosphingolipid-glycans using porous graphitized carbon (PGC) column, *Metabolites* 10 (2020) 433. 965
966
- [62] S. Eshghi, W. Yang, Y. Hu, P. Shah, S. Sun, X. Li, H. Zhang, Classification of tandem mass spectra for identification of N- and O-linked glycopeptides, *Sci. Rep.* 6 (2016) 37189. 967
968
- [63] E. Lattova, P. Strakova, P. Formanova, L. Grubhoffer, L. Bell-Sakyi, Z. Zdrahal, M. Palus, D. Ruzek, Comprehensive N-glycosylation mapping of envelope glycoprotein from tick-borne encephalitis virus grown in human and tick cells, *Sci. Rep.* 10 (2020) 13204. 969
970
971
- [64] M. Ardejani, L. Noodleman, E. Powers, J. Kelly, Stereoelectronic effects in stabilizing protein-N-glycan interactions revealed by experiment and machine learning, *Nat. Chem.* 480 (2021) 480–487. 972
973
- [65] B. Hamilton, J. Wilson, M. Shumakovich, A. Fisher, J. Brooks, A. Pontes, R. Naran, C. Heiss, C. Gao, R. Kardish, J. Heimburg-Molinari, P. Azadi, R. Cummings, J. Merritt, M. DeLisa, A library of chemically defined human N-glycans synthesized from microbial oligosaccharide precursors, *Sci. Rep.* 7 (2017) 15907. 974
975
976
- [66] C. Woodin, M. Maxon, H. Desaire, Software for automated interpretation of mass spectrometry data from glycans and glycopeptides, *Analyst* 138 (2013) 2793–2803. 977
978
- [67] D. Polasky, F. Yu, G. Teo, A. Nesvizhskii, Fast and comprehensive N- and O-glycoproteomics analysis with MSFragger-Glyco, *Nat. Met.* 17 (2020) 1125–1132. 979
980
- [68] B. Ivanova, M. Spiteller, Stochastic dynamic electrospray ionization mass spectrometric quantitative analysis of metronidazole in human urine, *Anal. Chem. Lett.* 12 (2022) 322–348. 981
982
- [69] C. Wang, C. Zhang, X. Gao, J. Lin, Isomer-specific biomarker discovery in multiple myeloma with dual-derivatized N-glycans, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* (2022) [<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-022-04010-w>]. 983
984
- [70] C. Liew, C. Yen, J. Chen, S. Tsai, S. Pawar, C. Wu, C. Ni, Structural identification of N-glycan isomers using logically derived sequence tandem mass spectrometry, *Nat. Commun. Chem.* 4 (2021) 92. 985
986
- [71] D. Harvey, Negative ion mass spectrometry for the analysis of N-Linked glycans, *Mass Spectrom. Rev.* 39 (2020) 586–679. 987
- [72] D. Harvey, W. Struwe, A. Behrens, S. Vasiljevic, M. Crispin, Formation and fragmentation of doubly and triply charged ions in the negative ion spectra of neutral N-glycans from viral and other glycoproteins, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 413 (2021) 7277–7294. 988
989
- [73] B. Ivanova, M. Spiteller, A stochastic dynamic mass spectrometric diffusion method and its application to 3D structural analysis of the analytes, *Rev. Anal. Chem.* 10.1515/revac-2019-0003 (2019). 990
991
- [74] B. Ivanova, M. Spiteller, Stochastic dynamic quantitative and 3D structural matrix assisted laser desorption/ionization mass spectrometric analyses of mixture of nucleosides, *J. Mol. Struct.* 1260 (2022) 132701. 992
993
- [75] B. Ivanova, M. Spiteller, Mass spectrometric stochastic dynamic 3D structural analysis of mixture of steroids in solution - Experimental and theoretical study, *Steroids* 181 (2022) 109001. 994
995
- [76] B. Ivanova, M. Spiteller, Stochastic dynamic electrospray ionization mass spectrometric diffusion parameters and 3D structural determination of complexes of AgI-ion – Experimental and theoretical treatment, *J. Mol. Liq.* 292 (2019) 111307. 996
997
- [77] B. Ivanova, M. Spiteller, A mass spectrometric stochastic dynamic diffusion approach to selective quantitative and 3D structural analyses of native cyclodextrins by electrospray ionization and atmospheric pressure chemical ionization methods, *Bioorg. Chem.* 93 (2019) 103308. 998
999
1000
- [78] B. Ivanova, M. Spiteller, Stochastic dynamic mass spectrometric approach to quantify reserpine in solution, *Anal. Chem. Lett.* 10 (2020) 703–721. 1001
1002
- [79] B. Ivanova, M. Spiteller, Stochastic dynamic mass spectrometric quantification of steroids in mixture – Part II, *Steroids* 164 (2020) article 108750. 1003
1004
- [80] R. Smith, Released N-glycans from IgG and Fetuin on Agilent QTOF and Orbitrap, (2021) DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4705545 (available since 20.04.2021.) 1005
1006
- [81] W. Zhang, W. Cao, J. Huang, H. Wang, J. Wan, C. Xie, P. Yang, PNGase F-mediated incorporation of ¹⁸O into glycans for relative glycan quantitation, *Analyst* 140 (2015) 1082–1089. 1007
1008
- [82] M. Vilaj, G. Lauc, I. Trbojevic-Akmacic, Evaluation of different PNGase F enzymes in immunoglobulin G and total plasma N-glycans analysis, *Glycobiol.* 31 (2021) 1. 1009
1010
- [83] J. Bodnar, A. Szekrenyes, M. Szigeti, G. Jarvas, J. Krenkova, F. Foret, A. Guttman, Enzymatic removal of N-glycans by PNGase F coated magnetic microparticles, *Electrophoresis* 37 (2016) 1264–1269. 1011
1012

- [84] M. Szigeti, J. Bondar, D. Gjerde, Z. Keresztessy, A. Szekrenyes, A. Guttman, Rapid N-glycan release from glycoproteins using immobilized PNGaseF microcolumns, *J. Chromatogr. B* 1032 (2016) 139–143. 1013
1014
- [85] A. Szekrenyes, J. Krenkova, Z. Keresztessy, F. Foret, A. Guttman, Oriented immobilization of PNGase F ion porous polymer monolith for rapid N-glycan realize, 9th International Interdisciplinary Meeting on Bioanalysis, Nov. 1–12, Brno, Czech Republic; (2012) 36–38. 1015
1016
1017
- [86] R. Torok, F. Auer, R. Farsang, E. Jona, G. Jarvas, A. Guttman, The effect of sample glucose content on PNGase F-mediated N-glycan release analyzed by capillary electrophoresis, *Molecules* 27 (2022) 8192. 1018
1019
- [87] B. Ivanova, M. Spiteller, Stochastic dynamics mass spectrometric 3D structural analysis of N-glycans of fetal bovine serum - an experimental and theoretical study, *Medical Sci. Forum* 14 (2022) 4. 1020
1021
- [88] B. Ivanova, M. Spiteller, Stochastic dynamics mass spectrometric 3D structural analysis of N-glycans of fetal bovine serum – an experimental and theoretical study, The 8th International Electronic Conference on Medicinal Chemistry (ECMC 2022), 01-30.11.2022 [sciforum-062459][<https://ecmc2022.sciforum.net/>]. 1022
1023
1024
- [89] E. Klontz, B. Trastoy, D. Deredge, J. Fields, C. Li, J. Orwenyo, A. Marina, R. Beadenkopf, S. Guenther, J. Flores, P. Wintrode, L. Wang, M. Guerin, E. Sundberg, Molecular basis of broad spectrum N-glycan specificity and processing of therapeutic IgG monoclonal antibodies by endoglycosidase S2, *ACS Cent. Sci.* 5 (2019) 524–538. 1025
1026
1027
- [90] Kelley, C. Iterative Methods for Optimization, *SIAM Front. Appl. Mathematics*, 18, 2009. 1028
- [91] Otto, M. Chemometrics, 3rd ed. Wiley, Weinheim, 2017, pp. 1–383. 1029
- [92] Apache OpenOffice, <http://de.openoffice.org>. 1030
- [93] D. Harvey, Collision-induced fragmentation of negative ions from N-linked glycans derivatized with 2-aminobenzoic acid, *J. Mass Spectrom.* 40 (2005) 642–653. 1031
1032
- [94] D. Gass, A. Quintero, J. Hatvany, E. Gallagher, Metal adduction in mass spectrometric analyses of carbohydrates and glycoconjugates, *Mass Spec Rev.* (2022) e21801. 1033
1034
- [95] B. Dommon, C. Costello. A Systematic Nomenclature for Carbohydrate Fragmentations in FAB-MS/MS Spectra of Glycoconjugates. *Glycoconjugate J.* 5 (1988) 397–409. 1035
1036
- [96] E. Stephens, S. Maslen, L. Green, D. Williams, Fragmentation Characteristics of Neutral N-linked Glycans Using a MALDI-TOF/TOF Tandem Mass Spectrometer. *Anal. Chem.* 76 (2004) 2343–2354. 1037
1038
- [97] E. Spina, D. Romeo, G. Impallomeni, D. Garozzo, D. Waidelich, M. Glueckmann, New fragmentation mechanisms in matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight/time-of-flight tandem mass spectrometry of carbohydrates. *Rapid Comm. Mass Spectrom.* 18 (2004) 392–398. 1039
1040
1041
- [98] D. Harvey, A. Merry, L. Royle, M. Campbell, R. Dwek, P. Rudd, Proposal for a standard system for drawing structural diagrams of N- and O-linked carbohydrates and related compounds, *Proteomics* 9 (2009) 3796–3801. 1042
1043
- [99] D. Harvey, Electrospray mass spectrometry and collision-induced fragmentation of 2-aminobenzamide-labelled neutral N-linked glycans, *Analyst* 125 (2000) 609–617. 1044
1045
- [100] D. Harvey, Electrospray mass spectrometry and fragmentation of N-linked carbohydrates derivatized at the reducing terminus, *J. Am. Soc. Mass Spectrom.* 11 (2000) 900–915. 1046
1047
- [101] X. Sun, L. Tao, L. Yi, Y. Ouyang, N. Xu, D. Li, R. Linhardt, Z. Zhang, N-glycans released from glycoproteins using a commercial kit and comprehensively analyzed with a hypothetical database, *J. Pharmaceut. Anal.* 7 (2017) 87–94. 1048
1049
- [102] L. Ruhaak, G. Zauner, C. Huhn, C. Bruggink, A. Deelder, M. Wuhrer, Glycan labeling strategies and their use in identification and quantification, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 397 (2010) 3457–3481. 1050
1051
- [103] N. Kawasaki, M. Ohta, S. Hyuga, O. Hashimoto, T. Hayakawa, Analysis of carbohydrate heterogeneity in a glycoprotein using liquid chromatography/mass spectrometry and liquid chromatography with tandem mass spectrometry, *Anal. Biochem.* 269 (1999) 297–303. 1052
1053
1054
- [104] J. Zaia, Mass spectrometry of oligosaccharides, *Mass Spectrom. Rev.* 23 (2004) 161–227. 1055
- [105] A. Ceroni, K. Maass, H. Geyer, R. Geyer, A. Dell, S. Haslam, GlycoWorkbench: A tool for the computer-assisted annotation of mass spectra of glycans, *J. Prot. Res.* 7 (2008) 1650–1659. 1056
1057
- [106] C. Yu, A. Mayampurath, H. Tang, Software tools for glycan profiling, *Methods Mol Biol.* (2013) 951. 1058
- [107] C. Woodin, M. Maxon, H. Desaire, Software for automated interpretation of mass spectrometry data from glycans and glycopeptides, *Analyst* 138 (2013) 2793–2803. 1059
1060
- [108] D. Harvey, Fragmentation of negative ions from carbohydrates: Part 2. Fragmentation of high-mannose N-linked glycans, *J. Am. Soc. Mass Spectrom.* 16 (2005) 631–646. 1061
1062
- [109] A. Devakumar, Y. Mechref, P. Kang, M. Novotny, J. Reilly, Identification of Isomeric N-Glycan Structures by Mass Spectrometry with 157 nm Laser-Induced Photofragmentation, *J Am Soc Mass Spectrom.* 19 (2008) 1027–1040. 1063
1064
- [110] M. Nakano, D. Higo, E. Arai, T. Nakagawa, K. Kakehi, N. Taniguchi, A. Kondo, Capillary electrophoresis-electrospray ionization mass spectrometry for rapid and sensitive N-glycan analysis of glycoproteins as 9-fluorenylmethyl derivatives, *Glycobiology* 19 (2009) 135–143. 1065
1066
1067
- [111] Y. Lin, L. Smith, Recognition of Functional Groups by Chemical Ionization Mass Spectrometry, *Biomed. Mass Spectrom.* 5 (1978) 604–611. 1068
1069
- [112] S. Schneider, E. Naegele, N-Glycan analysis of monoclonal antibodies and other glycoproteins using UHPLC with fluorescence detection, [www.agilent.com/chem/bio-inert] Agilent Technologies, Inc., 2012-2016 Published in the USA, May 1, 2016 5990-9774. 1070
1071
1072

- [113] N. Couto, L. Davlyatova, C. Evans, P. Wright, Application of the broadband collision-induced dissociation (bbCID) mass spectrometry approach for protein glycosylation and phosphorylation analysis. *Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom.* 32 (2018) 75–85. 1073–1075
- [114] Y. Xie, M. Butler, Construction of an InstantPC-derivatized glycan glucose unit database: A foundation work for high-throughput and high-sensitivity glycomic analysis, *Glycobiol.* 32 (2022) 289–303. 1076–1077
- [115] S. Gautam, W. Peng, B. Cho, Y. Huang, A. Banazadeh, A. Yu, X. Dong, Y. Mechref, Glucose unit index (GUI) of permethylated glycans for effective identification of glycans and glycan isomers, 145 (*Analyst*) 6656–6667. 1078–1079
- [116] B. Cho, W. Peng, Y. Mechref, Separation of permethylated O-glycans, free oligosaccharides, and glycosphingolipid-glycans using porous graphitized carbon (PGC) column, *Metabolites* 10 (2020) 433. 1080–1081
- [117] H. Yang, C. Yang, T. Sun, Characterization of glycopeptides using a stepped higher-energy C-trap dissociation approach on a hybrid quadrupole orbitrap, *Rapid Commun Mass Spectrom.* 32 (2018) 1353–1362. 1082–1083
- [118] Z. Darula, A. Pap, K. Medzihradzky, Extended sialylated O-glycan repertoire of human urinary glycoproteins discovered and characterized using electron-transfer/higher-energy collision dissociation, *J. Proteome Res.* 18 (2019) 280–291. 1084–1085
- [119] J. Kim, H. Hwang, J. Lim, H. Lee, S. Jeong, J. Yoo, Y. Paik, gFinder: A web-based bioinformatics tool for the analysis of N-glycopeptides, *J. Proteome Res.* 15 (2016) 4116–4125. 1086–1087
- [120] J. Lee, H. Lee, G. Park, H. Hwang, H. Jeong, K. Yun, E. Ji, K. Kim, J. Kim, J. Kim, S. Yun, C. Choi, S. Kim, J. Lim, S. Jeong, Y. Paik, S. Lee, J. Park, S. Kim, Y. Choi, Y. Kim, J. Seo, J. Cho, M. Oh, N. Seo, H. An, J. Kim, J. Yoo, Characterization of site-specific N-glycopeptide isoforms of α -1-acid glycoprotein from an interlaboratory study using LC-MS/MS, *J. Proteome Res.* 2015 (2016) 4146–4164. 1088–1091
- [121] C. Remoroza, Burke, X. Yang, S. Sheetlin, Y. Mirokhin, S. Markey, D. Tchekhovskoi, S. Stein, Mass spectral library methods for analysis of site-specific glycosylation: Application to human milk proteins, *J. Proteome Res.* 21 (2022) 2421–2434. 1092–1093
- [122] N. de Haan, Y. Narimatsu, M. Aasted, I. Larsen, I. Marinova, S. Dabelsteen, S. Vakhrushev, H. Wandall, In-depth profiling of O-glycan isomers in human cells using C18 nanoliquid chromatography-mass spectrometry and glycogenomics, *Anal. Chem.* 94 (2022) 4343–4351. 1094–1096
- [123] J. Hofmann, A. Stuckmann, M. Crispin, D. Harvey, K. Pagel, W. Struwe, Identification of lewis and blood group carbohydrate epitopes by ion mobility-tandem-mass spectrometry fingerprinting, *Anal. Chem.* 89 (2017) 2318–2325. 1097–1098
- [124] D. Harvey, W. Struwe, Structural studies of fucosylated N-glycans by ion mobility mass spectrometry and collision-induced fragmentation of negative ions, *J. Am. Soc. Mass Spectrom.* 29 (2018) 1179–1193. 1099–1100
- [125] N. de Haan, Y. Narimatsu, M. Aasted, I. Larsen, I. Marinova, S. Dabelsteen, S. Vakhrushev, H. Wandall, In-depth profiling of O-glycan isomers in human cells using C18 nanoliquid chromatography-mass spectrometry and glycogenomics, *Anal. Chem.* 94 (2022) 4343–4351. 1101–1103
- [126] J. Zhao, S. Li, C. Li, S. Wu, W. Xu, Y. Chen, M. Shameem, D. Richardson, H. Li, Identification of low abundant isomeric N-glycan structures in biological therapeutics by LC/MS, *Anal. Chem.* 88 (2016) 7049–7059. 1104–1105
- [127] L. Cao, J. Diedrich, Y. Ma, N. Wang, M. Pauthner, S. Park, C. Delahunty, J. McLellan, D. Burton, J. Yates, J. Paulson, Global site-specific analysis of glycoprotein N-glycan processing, *Nature* 13 (2018) 1196. 1106–1107
- [128] I. Breloy, S. Pacharra, P. Ottis, D. Bonar, A. Grahn, F. Hanisch, O-Linked N,N-Diacetyllactosamine (LacdiNAc)-modified Glycans in Extracellular Matrix Glycoproteins Are Specifically Phosphorylated at Subterminal N-Acetylglucosamine, *J. Biol. Chem.* 287 (2012) 18275–18286. 1108–1110
- [129] C. Wang, C. Zhang, X. Gao, J. Lin, Isomer-specific biomarker discovery in multiple myeloma with dual-derivatized N-glycans, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 414 (2022) 5617–5626. 1111–1112
- [130] Z. Klamer, P. Hsueh, D. Ayala-Talavera, B. Haab, Deciphering protein glycosylation by computational integration of on-chip profiling, glycan-array data, and mass spectrometry, *Mol. Cell. Proteom.* 18 (2019) 28–40. 1113–1114
- [131] K. Jiang, A. Aloor, J. Qu, C. Xiao, Z. Wu, C. Ma, L. Zhang, P. Wang, Rapid and sensitive MALDI MS analysis of oligosaccharides by using 2-hydrazinopyrimidine as a derivative reagent and co-matrix, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* DOI 10.1007/s00216-016-9690-x 1115–1117
- [132] Z. Darula, K. Medzihradzky, Affinity enrichment and characterization of mucin core-1 type glycopeptides from bovine serum, *Mol. Cell. Proteom.* 8 (2009) 2515–2526. 1118–1119
- [133] M. Windwarder, F. Altmann, Site-specific analysis of the O-glycosylation of bovine fetuin by electron-transfer dissociation mass spectrometry, *J. Proteom* 108 (2014) 258–268. 1120–1121
- [134] L. Bidondo, M. Landeira, F. Festari, T. Freire, C. Giacomini, A biotechnological tool for glycoprotein desialylation based on immobilized neuraminidase from *Clostridium perfringens*, *Biochem. Biophys. Rep.* 26 (2021) 100940. 1122–1123
- [135] C. Calvano, T. Cataldi, J. Koege, A. Monopoli, F. Palmisano, J. Sundermeyer, Structural characterization of neutral saccharides by negative ion MALDI mass spectrometry using a superbasic proton sponge as deprotonating matrix, *J. Am. Soc. Mass Spectrom.* 28 (2017) 1666–1675. 1124–1126
- [136] L. Hammad, D. Derryberry, Y. Jmeian, Y. Mechref, Quantification of monosaccharides through multiple-reaction monitoring liquid chromatography/mass spectrometry using an aminopropyl column, *Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom.* 24 (2010) 1565–1574. 1127–1129
- [137] A. Satoh, Introduction to practice of molecular simulation, 2011, Elsevier, Amsterdam, pp. 1 – 322. 1130
- [138] R. Kaur, Vikasa, Mechanisms for the inversion of chirality: Global reaction route mapping of stereochemical pathways in a probable chiral extraterrestrial molecule, 2-aminopropionitrile, *J. Chem. Phys.* 142, 074307 (2015) 1131–1132

- [139] A. Rohskopf, Sp. Wyant, K. Gordiz, H. Seyf, M. Muraleedharand, A. Henry, Fast and accurate interatomic potentials for describing thermal vibrations, *Computational Materials Science* 184 (2020) 109884 1133
1134
- [140] Z. Morrow, H. Kwon, C. Kelley, E. Jakubikova, Efficient Approximation of Potential Energy Surfaces with Mixed-Basis Interpolation, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* 2021, 17, 5673–5683. 1135
1136
- [141] B. Boychuk, Y. Jeong, S. Wetmore, Assessment of the accuracy of DFT-predicted Li⁺-nucleic acid binding energies, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* 17 (2021) 5392–5408. 1137
1138
- [142] Y. Liu, A. Dang, J. Urban, F. Turecek, Charge-tagged DNA radicals in the gas phase characterized by UV/Vis photodissociation action spectroscopy, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 59 (2020) 7772–7777. 1139
1140
- [143] B. Chan, Use of Low-Cost Quantum Chemistry Procedures for Geometry Optimization and Vibrational Frequency Calculations: Determination of Frequency Scale Factors and Application to Reactions of Large Systems, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* 13 (2017) 6052–6060. 1141
1142
1143
- [144] R. Freire, A. Simas, Sparkle/PM6 Parameters for all Lanthanide Trications from La(III) to Lu(III), *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* 6 (2010) 2019–2023; 1144
1145
- [145] J. Stewart, Optimization of parameters for semiempirical methods V: Modification of NDDO approximations and application to 70 elements, *J. Mol. Model.* 13 (2007) 1173–1213. 1146
1147
- [146] S. Perez-Tabero, B. Fernandez, E. Cabaleiro-Lago, E. Martínez-Nunez, S. Vazquez, New approach for correcting noncovalent interactions in semiempirical quantum mechanical methods: the importance of multiple-orientation sampling, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* 17 (2021) 5556–5567. 1148
1149
1150
- [147] J. Chen, J. Harper, J. Ho, Improving the accuracy of quantum mechanics/molecular mechanics (QM/MM) models with polarized fragment charges, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* (2022) <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.2c00491> 1151
1152
- [148] D. Demapan, J. Kussmann, C. Ochsenfeld, Q. Cui, Factors that determine the variation of equilibrium and kinetic properties of QM/MM enzyme simulations: QM region, conformation, and boundary condition. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* 18 (2022) 2530–2542. 1153
1154
1155
- [149] G. Box, M. Mueller, A note on the generation of random normal deviates, *Ann. Math. Stat.* 29 (1958) 610–611 1156
- [150] A. Satoh, Introduction to practice of molecular simulation: Molecular dynamics, Monte carlo, Brownian dynamics, Lattice Boltzmann, Dissipative particle dynamics; Elsevier insights Series, Elsevier, Amsterdam (2011) pp. 1–322. 1157
1158
- [151] R. Bader, T. Nguyen-Dang, Y. Tal, A topological theory of molecular structure, *Rep. Prog. Phys.* 44 (1981) 894–948. 1159
- [152] R. Zhang, J. Zhu, D. Lubman, Y. Mechref, H. Tang, GlycoHybridSeq: Automated identification of N-linked glycopeptides using electron transfer/high-energy collision dissociation (ETHcD), *J. Proteome Res.* 20 (2021) 3345–3352. 1160
1161
- [153] I. Walsh, S. Zhao, M. Campbell, C. Taron, P. Rudd, Quantitative profiling of glycans and glycopeptides: an informatics' perspective, *Curr. Opin. Struct. Biol.* 40 (2016) 70–80. 1162
1163
- [154] G. Xu, X. Liu, Q. Liu, Y. Zhou, J. Li, Improve accuracy and sensibility in glycan structure prediction by matching glycan isotope abundance, *Anal. Chim. Acta* 743 (2012) 80–89. 1164
1165
- [155] O. Serang, J. Froehlich, J. Muntel, G. McDowell, H. Steen, R. Lee, J. Steen, SweetSEQer, Simple *de novo* filtering and annotation of glycoconjugate mass spectra, *Mol. Cell. Proteom.* 12 (2013) 1735–1740, 1166
1167
- [156] M. Campbell, T. Nguyen-Khuong, C. Hayes, S. Flowers, K. Alagesan, D. Kolarich, N. Packer, N. Karlsson, Validation of the curation pipeline of UniCarb-DB: Building a global glycan reference MS/MS repository, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta* 1844 (2014) 108–116. 1168
1169
1170
- [157] D. Velickovic, T. Becejac, S. Mamedov, K. Sharma, N. Ambalavanan, T. Alexandrov, C. Anderton, Rapid automated annotation and analysis of N-glycan mass spectrometry imaging data sets using NGlycDB in METASPACE, *Anal. Chem.* 93 (2021) 13421–13425. 1171
1172
1173
- [158] D. Bui, J. Jung, E. Kitova, Z. Li, S. Willows, M. Boddington, P. Kitov, A. Mason, C. Capicciotti, L. Mahal, M. Macauley, J. Klarsen, Mass spectrometry-based shotgun glycomics using labeled glycan libraries, *Anal. Chem.* 94 (2022) 4997–5005. 1174
1175
- [159] D. Ivanov, Y. Yang, J. Pawlowski, I. Carrick, I. Kaltashov, Rapid evaluation of the extent of haptoglobin glycosylation using orthogonal intact-mass MS approaches and multivariate analysis, *Anal. Chem.* 94 (2022) 5140–5148. 1176
1177
- [160] S. Eshghi, P. Shah, W. Yang, X. Li, H. Zhang, GPQuest: A spectral library matching algorithm for site-specific assignment of tandem mass spectra to intact N-glycopeptides, *Anal. Chem.* 87 (2015) 5181–5188. 1178
1179
- [161] W. Skala, T. Wohlschlagler, S. Senn, G. Huber, C. Huber, MoFi: A software tool for annotating glycoprotein mass spectra by integrating hybrid data from the intact protein and glycopeptide level, *Anal. Chem.* 90 (2018) 5728–5736. 1180
1181
- [162] M. Pioch, M. Hoffmann, A. Pralow, U. Reichl, E. Rapp, glyXtoolMS: An open-source pipeline for semiautomated analysis of glycopeptide mass spectrometry data, *Anal. Chem.* 90 (2018) 11908–11916. 1182
1183
- [163] L. Lee, E. Moh, B. Parker, M. Bern, N. Packer, M. Thaysen-Andersen, Toward automated N-glycopeptide identification in glycoproteomics, *J. Proteome Res.* 15 (2016) 3904–3915. 1184
1185
- [164] N. Miura, H. Hanamatsu, I. Yokota, K. Okada, J. Furukawa, Y. Shinohara, Toolbox accelerating glycomics (TAG): Glycan annotation from MALDI-TOF MS spectra and mapping expression variation to biosynthetic pathways, *Biomolecules* 10 (2020) 1383. 1186
1187
1188
- [165] Y. Wang, D. Bu, C. Huang, H. Wang, J. Zhou, J. Dong, W. Pan, J. Zhang, Q. Zhang, Y. Li, S. Sun, Best-first search guided multistage mass spectrometry-based glycan identification, *Bioinformatics* 35 (2019) 2991–2997. 1189
1190
- [166] D. Weatherly, F. Arpinar, M. Porterfield, M. Tiemeyer, W. York, R. Ranzinger, GRITS Toolbox - a freely available software for processing, annotating and archiving glycomics mass spectrometry data, *Glycobiology* 29 (2019) 452–460. 1191
1192

-
- [167] S. Boecker, B. Kehr, F. Rasche, Determination of glycan structure from tandem mass Spectra, *IEEE/ACM Trans. Comput. Biol. Bioinf.* 8 (2011) 976–986. 1193
1194
- [168] R. Zhang, W. Peng, S. Gautam, Y. Huang, Y. Mechref, H. Tang, GlycanGUI: Automated glycan annotation and quantification using glucose unit index, *Front. Chem.* 9 (2021) 707382. 1195
1196
- [169] M. Wang, G. Yu, Y. Mechref, H. Resson, GPA: An algorithm for LC/MS based glycan profile annotation, *IEEE Int. Conf. Bioinform. Biomed.* (2013) 16–22. 1197
1198
- [170] D. Polasky, F. Yu, G. Teo, A. Nesvizhskii, Fast and comprehensive *N*- and *O*-glycoproteomics analysis with MSFragger-Glyco, *Nat. Met.* 17 (2020) 1125–1132. 1199
1200
- [171] C. Lia, Y. Tiana, J. Han, Y. Lu, M. Zou, Y. Jia, C. Wang, L. Huang, Z. Wang, An innovative method used for the identification of *N*-glycans on soybean allergen β -conglycinins, *Food Sci. Hum. Well.* 12 (2023) 842–851. 1201
1202
1203
1204